

Leaflets and Online Guidance on Participatory Media Practices

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Executive summary

This deliverable outlines the communication, dissemination and first exploitation activities conducted by the WP6 partners to inform, promote and disseminate the results and learnings of the Citizens' Parliaments on Media and Democracy. It also indicates avenues for further exploitation of the results and learnings gathered within the MeDeMAP project.

The Citizens' Parliaments (CPs) on Media and Democracy were organized by the WP6 partners COMMIT in Austria, Charles University (CU) in the Czech Republic, the Peace Institute (Mirovni Institut, MI) in Slovenia and Mary Immaculate College (MIC) in Limerick, Ireland between March and May 2025 as part of the MeDeMAP project, to involve citizens in the research process. The results of the four CPs take the form of resolutions on media and democracy adopted by the citizens.

The first section of this report documents the communication activities of the four national Citizens' Parliaments from the recruitment call to the promotion of the results, i.e. the national resolutions adopted by the citizens. The second section provides information on how the WP6 partners disseminated the Citizens' Parliaments results and the knowledge gained from implementing the Citizens' Parliaments in relation to the field of media and democracy. The third section details the actions taken so far by the WP6 partners and their plans for further exploitation of the results of the Citizens' Parliaments. The conclusion summarises the learnings from the dissemination activities and makes recommendations for future work of and with Citizens' Parliaments. Detailed lists of partners' activities for communication and dissemination and some visual examples of their communication materials and publications (e.g. flyers, posters, leaflets, infographics) can be found in Appendix 1 and 2.

The report is supplemented by two leaflets that showcase good practices for Media and Information Literacy and for Community Media and media participation in the WP6 partner countries, in connection with the respective resolutions on these two topics adopted in the Citizens' Parliaments. These leaflets are included as Appendix 3.

Introduction

With work package 6, “Supply meets demand”, citizens have become involved in an active role in the MeDeMAP research project on media and democracy. By participating in the Citizens' Parliaments on Media and Democracy in Austria, Czech Republic, Ireland, and Slovenia, they have significantly influenced the research results and formulated their own recommendations for the further development of a pro-democratic media policy and media landscape.

The term Citizens' Parliament is used in the project as one form of deliberative “mini-publics”, which is the more generic term widely used in academic literature to describe various deliberative participatory processes involving citizens, such as citizens' councils, parliaments, assemblies, or forums (see Monnot et al., 2025a, p. 10).

Through the process of the Citizens' Parliaments, the citizens were enabled to adopt concrete resolutions on media and democracy, which have been promoted at a national and European level and are further disseminated to stakeholders. Furthermore, the process and results of the Citizens' Parliaments have also provided research material on media and democracy as well as participatory processes for the WP6 partners within the MeDeMAP project, who disseminate their research results in the academic sphere and beyond. The experience of implementing the citizens' parliaments has especially generated knowledge and know-how on the potential of Citizens' Parliaments to support renewal and strengthening of democracy. WP6 partners have been disseminating this know-how with an aim of opening paths for further exploitation.

One of the challenges faced by most Citizens' Parliaments is having visibility to influence policy-making. However, reaching decision-makers from the media, politics, and society was a definite goal set by the Citizens' Parliaments on Media and Democracy. Despite having limited resources, the WP6 partners, COMMIT in Austria, Charles University (CU) in the Czech Republic, Mary Immaculate College (MIC) in Ireland, and the Mirovni Institute / Peace Institute (MI) in Slovenia, developed extensive communication campaigns. These campaigns aimed at encouraging citizens to participate in the Citizens' Parliaments, mobilising stakeholders in support of the project, raising awareness of the issue of media and democracy, and presenting the results to the broader public and various stakeholders. The WP6 partners are continuing to disseminate the resolutions on media and democracy adopted by their Citizens' Parliaments, the research results as well as the knowledge gained from the implementation processes in academic and non-academic contexts, offering several avenues for exploiting the results for societal and political purposes.

The online Citizens' Parliament with German participants, which was conducted as a methodological experiment by OEAW, is not included in this report. The online CP was organized to test the implementation of a CP in an online setting. The results of this experiment will be disseminated in an academic paper by OEAW.

1. Communication activities from the recruitment call to the promotion of the results of the Citizens' Parliaments

Communication is defined by Horizon Europe (2023) as activities developed to “*inform, promote and communicate activities and results*” towards citizens, stakeholders and the media. Although the design of the Citizens' Parliaments was based on a common model developed in Deliverable 6.2, “Design of Citizens' Parliaments” (Monnot et al., 2025b), communication with citizens and national stakeholders was adapted to local contexts and largely depended on each partner's communication networks and supportive environment.

Communication was also affected by two factors: the country's existing tradition of citizens' parliaments, and the current level of interest in the issue of media and democracy among the public and stakeholders. While citizens' parliaments have some tradition in Austria and Ireland, they were a pioneering event in the Czech Republic.

In Austria and Slovenia, the political agenda helped draw the attention of the media and political stakeholders to the citizens' parliaments. These took place at a time when a new government, tasked with reforming media policy, was taking office in Austria, and when a new media law was being drafted by the Ministry of Culture and subsequently adopted by the National Assembly in September 2025 in Slovenia.

Based on the Research Report on Successful Practices with Citizens' Parliaments in Europe (Deliverable 6.1, Monnot et al., 2025a), COMMIT developed communication guidelines for the partners. These included recommendations for informing Citizens' Parliaments participants, stakeholders and the general public, and for promoting transparency. The guidelines also suggest a range of communication activities, such as creating a dedicated webpage, issuing press releases and participating in round-table discussions, as well as making use of social networks.

Each WP6 partner developed their own outreach strategy according to their respective networks and their national and local context. Two key moments in the communication activities were the call for participation before the Citizens' Parliaments launch and the national presentations of the results. Due to budget constraints, all communication tasks were carried out by the project team members. Details on the WP6-partners communication activities are included in Appendix 1.

Involving partners and stakeholders

To advertise the Citizens' Parliaments to the public, increase the outreach of the call to prospective participants, and involve stakeholders in media policy, the WP6 partners mobilised their diverse networks and partners in academia, the media sector, and civil society for their communication. The Austrian, Czech and Irish CPs were supported by a formal advisory board consisting of members of civil society and various stakeholders from the field of media and education, while the Slovenian CP relied on exchange with key stakeholders, as well as on mobilising its networks in civil society organisations, professional associations, academia and

media outlets for promotion, communication, and dissemination of results, reflecting MI's position as part of both civil society and academia.

To ensure transparency and build trust, the composition of the formal advisory boards of the Austrian, Czech and Irish CPs was included in the partners' CP documentation:

- The Austrian advisory board included 8 members from organizations representing the media, social partners, adult education, research, and the city of Vienna (see: <https://medemap.commit.at/die-menschen/#beirat>).
- The Czech advisory council counted 10 members representing the media, as well as NGOs, the research field, and a platform for Citizen Assemblies (see: <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/op/poradni-skupina-pro-obcansky-parlament-o-mediich-a-demokracii/>).
- The Irish advisory board included seven members, including the mayor of Limerick and representatives from various media outlets and research institutions (see: <https://www.mic.ul.ie/MeDeMap?index=3>).

The advisory boards' role included providing support with:

- reaching out to and networking with decision-makers and relevant stakeholders;
- helping with the recruitment of participants and experts;
- communicating about the process of the CPs and disseminating the resolutions and other results;

For the Slovenian CP, no formal advisory board was established, as the Peace Institute (Mirovni Institut – MI) – a scientific research organisation and an NGO with public-interest status in human rights protection, anti-discrimination, media, and international development cooperation – relied on its extensive, long-standing networks in academia, media, and civil society. These networks were actively involved throughout the process, supporting outreach and recruitment of a diverse participant pool, assisting with organisational tasks (such as securing appropriate premises and engaging the student radio to record CP sessions), and contributing to the communication and dissemination of results. A particularly important role was played by The Voice of the People, a large civil-society network connecting more than 100 organisations and informal civic groups, whose informal coordination body meets weekly, circulates updates to several thousand activists, and includes members experienced in organising ad-hoc people's assemblies. Along with contacts in academic networks and media and journalists' associations, this coordination body provided ongoing consultation and effectively served as an informal advisory structure for the Peace Institute throughout the preparation, implementation, and follow-up of the CP on Media and Democracy in Slovenia.

Communication online

The WP6 MeDeMAP Blog

As part of the WP6 task, COMMIT created a blog-site for the general public, to which partners contributed with articles on the progress after each meeting of their Citizens' Parliament, from launch to national-level results presentation. The aim was to make not only the results but also the CP process easy to follow and understandable for interested parties and serve as a template for future CPs. More details on the blog and the blog posts are documented in

Deliverable 6.3, “Blog on citizens’ parliaments” (Monnot et al., 2025c). All blog posts can be found here: <https://medemap.commit.at/medemap-blog/>.

Webpages of the partners' websites and social media platforms

Each WP6 partner created a subpage on their institution's website and shared information on their social media profiles.

COMMIT:

- Project webpage: <https://medemap.commit.at/>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/communitymedieninstitut>
- Bluesky: <https://bsky.app/profile/commit-at.bsky.social>
- Mastodon: https://mastodon.social/@COMMIT_at
- Facebook: <https://facebook.com/CommunityMedienInstitut>

Charles University (CU):

- Project webpage: <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/op/>
- Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/iksz_fsv_uk/?hl=en

Mary Immaculate College (MIC):

- Project webpage: <https://www.mic.ul.ie/MeDeMap?index=0>

Mirovni Institut (MI):

- Project webpage: <https://www.mirovni-institut.si/mediji-demokracija/>
- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/mirovni.institut.si/>
- Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/mirovni_institut/

Recruitment and information campaigns

To inform stakeholders and the public about the upcoming Citizens' Parliaments and recruit a pool of 24 diverse participants (including a reserve list of four), each partner launched a far-reaching campaign. Advisory board members, partner organisations, and media were asked to share information about the CPs in articles, radio shows, newsletters or on social media.

Campaigns at a national level

COMMIT worked with their national network of community media, including Radio Orange 94.0 and Okto TV in Vienna, Radio FRO in Linz and several other community broadcasters outside the capital to advertise the call for participants and disseminate information on the Citizens' Parliaments – including a large TV-report on the national presentation. Two local Vienna print media (among them *Mein Wien* with a circulation of 1.3 million copies reaching most city households) and the national daily *Der Standard* disseminated the call in Austria. A press release distributed through the network of the Austrian press agency (APA) reached the entire media industry. Postcards advertising the CPs were disseminated in public institutions and civil society organisations. Additionally, COMMIT gave interviews to diverse community media, participated in a public discussion on participatory democracy and distributed their call for participation at diverse events.

Charles University (CU) started communicating on the up-coming Czech Citizens' Parliaments as early as August 2024 with a press release from CU and a social media campaign. The press release was further relayed by members of the Advisory Board. A leaflet was disseminated and the CU team participated in discussions on participatory democracy. The reputed Czech newspaper *Deník N* published a 2-page opinion article about citizen parliaments and the call

for participants, and ads with a call for participants were also published on the reputed Czech media *Alarm*, *dobrovolnik.cz* and *Respekt*.

For the recruitment of participants and the information on the Irish CP, Mary Immaculate College (MIC) implemented an extensive campaign including paid advertising, interviews given to the media, free posting on online media, and the distribution of posters. Space (including online dissemination) was bought in two media outlets, the Limerick Leader (150,000 readers and 149,000 followers its social media platform) and the Post Newspaper (200,000 readers). MIC's radio campaign included interviews on national radio with

- The public service broadcaster RTÉ Radio 1 (RTÉ overall reach: 28.5% of Irish radio listeners),
- Raidió na Gaeltachta (0.4% listeners, content in Irish),
- local commercial radio, Limerick Live95 (93,000 listeners weekly and 10,000 listeners every quarter hour).
- Community Radio stations.

MIC's media and radio campaign was complemented by a poster campaign in over thirty locations across Limerick City and County, and by making face-to-face contact with potential participants. MIC also contacted various local organisations, such as local community choirs or a local youth outreach centre, etc. to address potential participants. Social media and the MIC website were also utilised.

To advertise its public call for applications, the Peace Institute (MI) in Slovenia informed on its website and its social media Instagram and Facebook, and sent repeated newsletters. The call for participants was also disseminated through two online media outlets – non-profit community media and political weekly. To ensure diversity and reach an audience beyond the capital Ljubljana, various organisations (including civil society NGOs, volunteer associations, and other community groups) were asked to forward the call to their members and networks. Additionally, pamphlets and posters were displayed in multiple locations around Ljubljana and distributed in public spaces.

Campaign at the European level

COMMIT works to support media literacy in adult education and community media, so it was right placed to communicate about the Citizens' Parliaments on the Electronic Platform for Adult Learning in Europe (EPALE), addressed to the European community engaged in adult education. COMMIT has published an article in both a German and English version on EPALÉ at the start of the Citizens' Parliaments and will follow up with another article about the results of the four CPs at the end of the project. COMMIT has also communicated about the Citizens' Parliaments via Community Media Forum Europe (CMFE), the European network of community media.

The national presentations of the Citizens' Parliaments results to the general public and stakeholders

The results of the four citizens' parliaments were presented to the general public, civil society, the media and policymakers at a national level. These national presentations provided an opportunity for both communication and dissemination (see also the next section).

COMMIT, CU, MIC and MI each reported on their national presentations in a blog post on the WP6 MeDeMAP Blog (<https://medemap.commit.at/medemap-blog/>):

- Czech national presentation of the CP's results in the Senate of the Czech Republic on 5 June 2025. <https://medemap.commit.at/the-czech-citizen-parliament-on-media-and-democracy-submits-its-resolutions-to-the-senate-of-the-czech-republic/>
- Slovenian national presentation of the CP's results at the Ministry of Culture on 9 June 2025. <https://medemap.commit.at/public-presentation-of-slovenian-citizens-parliament-demands/>
- Austrian national presentation of the CP's results at Concordia press club on 25 June 2025. <https://medemap.commit.at/the-austrian-citizens-parliament-on-media-and-democracy-presents-its-demands/>
- Irish national presentation of the CP's results at the Joint Oireachtas (Parliamentary Committee) on Arts, Media, Communications and Culture. <https://medemap.commit.at/the-irish-citizens-parliament-on-media-and-democracy-presented-its-resolutions-to-the-irish-joint-parliamentary-committee/>

2. Dissemination of the Citizens' Parliaments results and of the knowledge gained on the CP process

Horizon Europe (2023) defines dissemination as an action conducted to “*make knowledge and results publicly available free-of-charge*” directed at “*those who can learn and benefit from the results, such as: scientists, industry, public authorities, policymakers, civil society*” in the form of publications in scientific magazines, conferences, or databases.

Each partner was responsible for setting up its outreach strategy and encouraged to identify the best ways to reach out to decision-makers and interested groups to maximize the impact of the CPs' resolutions and outcomes.

The results of the citizens' parliaments on media and democracy were disseminated at local, regional, national and European level and were addressed to the research community, as well as to institutions and civic organisations working in the field of media and democracy.

Disseminating the Citizens' Parliaments resolutions to stakeholders at national and European levels

Each WP6 partner developed a dissemination strategy based on its area of expertise (research or civil society) and its networks. Nevertheless, common events marked some milestones of their dissemination activities concerning the CP resolutions.

National dissemination of the CP results and National Resolutions reports

National presentations of the CP results

COMMIT: The resolutions of the Austrian CP were presented at the Austrian Press Club Concordia on 25 June 2025. After the presentation, representatives of the vice-chancellor in charge of media policy, of the ministries of education and culture, and of the media industry participated in a roundtable discussion. More details: <https://medemap.commit.at/the-austrian-citizens-parliament-on-media-and-democracy-presents-its-demands/>.

Charles University (CU): The Czech Citizen Parliament presented its resolutions at a roundtable in the Senate on 5 June 2025 under the auspices of the 1st Deputy Chairman of the Senate. The event was organised in collaboration with the Institute of Communication Studies and Journalism at Charles University, the Open Society Foundations (OSF) and the Independent Journalism Endowment Fund (NFNZ). More details: <https://medemap.commit.at/the-czech-citizen-parliament-on-media-and-democracy-submits-its-resolutions-to-the-senate-of-the-czech-republic/>

Mary Immaculate College (MIC): The results of the Irish CP were first presented at the level of local democracy in Limerick July 14th, 2025, at the local authority meeting, i.e. Limerick City and County Council. This was reported in the local media and the resolutions were discussed by the councillors in the chamber and afterwards with the 10 citizens who had attended. In November, ten members of the Irish Citizens' Parliament travelled to Dublin to present their resolutions to the Joint Parliamentary Committee on Arts, Media, and Communications (made

up of Members of Parliament and Senators). The Joint Committee is currently redrafting its media legislation and informed the citizens that the resolutions will be examined and taken into consideration for future legislation. The presentation was broadcast live on national television and is available to view here: <https://www.oireachtas.ie/en/oireachtas-tv/video-archive/committees/?datePeriod=dates&fromDate=05%2F11%2F2025&toDate=05%2F11%2F2025&committee=%2Fen%2Fcommittees%2F34%2Farts-media-communications-culture-and-sport%2F>.

The resolutions were also presented to other stakeholders, specifically The Irish regulator, Coimisiún na Meán (the Commission for Media), the National Union of Journalists (NUJ) and the NGO, Media Literacy Ireland. These stakeholders will also consider how resolutions that relate to their remit can be implemented. More details: <https://medemap.commit.at/the-irish-citizens-parliament-on-media-and-democracy-presented-its-resolutions-to-the-irish-joint-parliamentary-committee/>

Peace Institute (MI): CP members and the researchers involved in the Slovenian CP presented their demands at an event held at the Ministry of Culture on 9 June 2025. It was attended by high-ranking ministry officials, Members of Parliament, as well as media representatives from the Association of Journalists, RTV Slovenia's Ombudsman, individual editors, and journalists from the public service broadcaster, the Slovenian Press Agency STA, and the non-profit media outlet Oštro. Representatives from civil society and academia were also present. More [details](#). In addition, findings from the MeDeMAP project, with an emphasis on the CP resolutions and broader media-democracy issues, were publicly presented at the Naprej/Forward journalism festival in Maribor on 14 November 2025, to journalists and an interested public. Finally, MI is organising a national final project event in Slovenia at the end of February 2026, bringing together stakeholders, journalists, and citizens to present the project results and open a public discussion on their implications.

The National Resolutions Reports

The National Resolutions Reports, which include documentation on the CP's process and the resolutions adopted by citizens, were edited in the local languages and in English. They were made available in print and PDF formats for distribution at events and meetings, as well as online. Here are the English and original language versions:

The Austrian Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy:

- (EN) https://www.commit.at/fileadmin/Materialien/MeDeMap/COMMIT_CPA-Report_A4_EN.pdf
- (DE) https://www.commit.at/fileadmin/Materialien/MeDeMap/Buergerinnenrat-Medien-Demokratie_Bericht-A4_web.pdf

The Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy:

- (EN) https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/CZ_CP_ResolutionsReport_EN.pdf
- (CZ) <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/Cesky-obcansky-parlament-o-mediich-a-demokracii-3.pdf>

The Irish Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy:

- (EN) https://issuu.com/micireland/docs/report_-_national_citizens_parliament_on_media_an?fr=sN2NjOTg0MzIzMjM

The Slovenian Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy:

- (EN) https://www.mirovni-institut.si/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/ANG_zachteve-zbora_booklet-web.pdf
- (SI) https://www.mirovni-institut.si/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/zbor-obcanov_web.pdf

Dissemination of the resolutions towards national stakeholders and policy-makers

The WP6 partners are committed to further disseminating the CPs' results to their national stakeholders, including representatives of political parties responsible for media and fundamental rights policy, media regulation authorities, representative organisations from the media industry and journalist unions, professional consumer representatives, chambers of commerce and NGOs active in the fields of social justice, minority group support and media freedom.

COMMIT held two follow-up discussions with the media spokespersons and members of the National Council of the two governing parties SPÖ (Klaus Seltenheim) and ÖVP (Nico Marchetti) to present the resolutions of the Austrian CP for a potential uptake in policy making. COMMIT also presented resolutions from all countries in a meeting with Wolfgang Struber, the managing director of the Austrian media authority RTR and his colleagues responsible for Media and Information Literacy policy. Mr. Struber was interested to invite CP-members for an event later in 2026.

CU published three infographics advertising the resolutions of the Czech CP on the role of the media, media literacy and community media, and explored artistic dissemination with the production of the short film *Agon: Constructions of Democracy* (Minanto, Carpentier, & Purwanto, 2025, <http://www.constructionsofdemocracy.eu/>), based on the book *Democracy and Media in Europe* by Nico Carpentier and Jeffrey Wimmer (2025).

MIC presented the work and resolutions of the Irish CP to a high level group including the Minister for Communications, the Press Ombudsman, a Commissioner from Coimisiún na Meán and 27 other representatives of national bodies at a conference on Disinformation organized by Media Literacy Ireland in Mary Immaculate College, Limerick in June 2026.

In Slovenia, dissemination activities combined public outreach, direct engagement with policy-makers, and targeted communication with regulatory and institutional stakeholders. The resolutions of the Citizens' Parliament were presented to the general public through a public broadcaster programme (RTVsmo) on RTV Slovenia's First Programme, where CP resolutions on media and democracy were discussed. The CP resolutions were also referenced in the policy-making process at the national level, notably during the second reading of the Media Act at the National Assembly's Cultural Committee. During the session, MI project leader referred to the resolutions of the Citizens' Parliament in the discussion on media regulation, addressing members of parliament, invited experts, and representatives of media and journalists' associations. In addition, hard copies of the CP resolutions were disseminated by post to key institutional stakeholders, including members of the National Assembly's Cultural Committee, the Minister of Culture, the Agency for Communication Networks and Services of the Republic of Slovenia (AKOS), the Media Inspectorate of the Republic of Slovenia, and the Council of RTV Slovenia.

Dissemination of the Citizens' Parliaments resolutions at the European level

The resolutions of the four Citizens' Parliaments were presented jointly to Members of the European Parliament (MEPs), representatives of the European Commission, as well as to media and NGO representatives on January 13, 2026, at a roundtable discussion on “*What do European citizens have to teach EU media policy?*” in the EU Parliament in Brussels. The event was organized as part of the seminar, “*Regulating Media for Future Democracies: Political and People’s Voices*” hosted by Irena Joveva MEP (Renew Europe) and co-hosted by MEP Marina Kaljurand (Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats) within the framework of the MeDeMAP project. At the CP roundtable, two delegates from each CP addressed a selection of demands with a European dimension at the European Parliament. They received responses from two MEPs who were invited to the roundtable: Hannes Heide (Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats) and Lena Schilling (Greens/European Free Alliance). The meeting was attended by several MEPs from each of the countries that had held a Citizens’ Parliament as well as from other countries represented in the MeDeMAP Project. Further details of this event can be found on the WP6 MeDeMAP Blog: <https://medemap.commit.at/the-citizens-parliaments-on-media-and-democracy-present-their-results-in-the-european-parliament-in-brussels/>

Two leaflets, highlighting two specific re-occurring topics in the resolutions of all four Citizens’ Parliaments – Media and Information Literacy and Community media and media participation – were produced by the WP6 partners as an annex to this report (see Appendix 3). The leaflets present good practice examples on Media and Information Literacy and on Community Media and media participation from Austria, the Czech Republic, Ireland and Slovenia, in line with the CP resolutions.

To disseminate the results of the Citizens’ Parliaments on a European level, COMMIT also published an article in the newspaper of the European Civic Forum (ECF) Archipel (in German and French, see <https://forumcivique.org/artikel/oesterreich-buergerinnenraete-medien-und-demokratie/>). COMMIT will further disseminate the results of the CPs, including the two leaflets, via the Community Media Forum Europe (CMFE) mailing list. CMFE is the leading network advocating for community media across Europe. Similarly, the results relating to media literacy will be presented at an upcoming meeting of the EMIL network of the European Forum of National or Regional Audiovisual Regulators (EPRA).

Disseminating the results and know-how gained through the Citizens’ parliaments processes in academic and non-academic contexts

The results of the Citizens’ Parliaments were not only disseminated as resolutions aimed at policymakers and other stakeholders, but they were also an object of the research conducted by the WP6 partners. Research results and the knowledge and know-how gained through the implementation of the CPs were disseminated by the WP6 partners in various academic and non-academic contexts.

Dissemination activities about the CP format and results: The round table "Citizens' parliaments as a democratic innovation"

A round table on "Citizens' parliaments as a democratic innovation" was organised by COMMIT at the University of Applied Science in St. Pölten during the MeDeMAP project Meeting on September 24, 2025, to discuss the process and the results of the CPs. The event was public and streamed online to allow for wider dissemination.

In a first panel, COMMIT, CU, MIC and MI presented the process, the results, and the learnings from the CPs. A second panel brought together experts on citizen participation from academia and policy to discuss the impact and opportunities of participatory democracy and the ways in which citizens' parliaments have established themselves as a policymaking tool. The practices in the Austrian regions of Vorarlberg and Vienna were used as examples. Further details of this event can be found on the WP6 MeDeMAP Blog: <https://medemap.commit.at/citizens-parliaments-as-a-democratic-innovation-roundtable-at-the-final-medemap-project-meeting/>

Dissemination of the results of the Citizens' Parliaments in academic and non-academic publications and at conferences

The results from the national and aggregate analyses of the Citizens' Parliaments within the MeDeMAP project were disseminated in MeDeMAP Deliverable 6.4 (Sedlaczek et al., 2026) and will also be the object of an academic article by OEAW. This research analysed the process and results of the Citizens' Parliaments against the background of the theoretical framework of democracy and media developed in Work Package 2 of the MeDeMAP project (Carpentier & Wimmer, 2025). The aims of the research were to map how European citizens envision the way media in Europe can better fulfil their democratic roles, and to reflect the participatory process of the Citizens' Parliament.

Each partner developed a dissemination strategy for their own academic and non-academic publications on the CP results and participated in panels or conferences relevant to their field of work, resulting, for instance, in presentations at the IAMCR 2025 Singapore conference, at the CEECOM 2025 Conference (Zadar, Croatia), at the Department of Communications Seminar at the Universitas Islam Indonesia (Yogyakarta, Indonesia), at the Policy Lab Learning Webinar of the Institute of Policy Studies (IPS) (Singapore) and at the 11th MCAP-BNU International Media Conference 2026 in Lahore (Pakistan). Further presentations, for instance at IAMCR 2026 (Galway), are already planned.

The WP6 partners also organised a series of events to disseminate their research results to an academic audience. A panel on "Civic Participation, Media and Democracy", with presentations on the Slovenian, Czech and Irish CPs, took place at the MeDeMAP conference "Beyond the Audience: Rethinking Participation and Power in the Age of Data Capitalism", organised by IULM University in Rome on 15–16 January 2026. CU organised a public panel in Prague on 28 January 2026 with the title "Seminar On The Czech Citizen Parliament: Analysing Media Change, Participation, and Democracy".

Appendix 2 provides an overview of the partners' dissemination activities, including their academic publications and conference presentations.

Dissemination of the CP-format to stakeholders at national, European and international levels

The WP6 partners have also been involved in disseminating the knowledge and know-how gained from implementing the CPs and reflecting on the participatory process to various academic and non-academic institutions and stakeholders who can take these results further. This includes expertise in the design and implementation process, as well as reflections on how participation in a CP can be used as a learning tool.

CU, for example, held a Policy Lab Learning Webinar on “*Citizens’ Parliaments: Lessons in Public Participation*” for the Institute of Policy Studies (IPS) (Singapore) in October 2025, sharing their experiences and insights from the Czech CP to support policymakers and practitioners to expand their public engagement practice.

COMMIT has published several non-academic articles on Citizens' Parliaments as participatory learning spaces for democracy education on platforms and in publications from adult education institutions, such as the European Adult Education Platform (EPALE) (two articles), the Austrian adult education platform <https://erwachsenenbildung.at/> (one article) and the quarterly print magazine of the Austrian organisation of adult education centres (one article). COMMIT is currently also preparing an academic article on this topic.

3. Exploitation of results

Horizon Europe (2023) defines exploitation as activities aiming at “*a concrete use of results for commercial, societal and political purposes for those who can take the results forward or invest in them, such as: researchers, stakeholders, industry (also SMEs), public authorities, policymakers, civil society*” in the form of roadmaps, prototypes, sharing knowledge, skills, or data.

According to their diverse fields of work, the WP6 partners have started to target exploitation at academic, policy and/or societal levels, developing different paths or tools under the framework of various partnerships.

Despite limited resources, COMMIT, CU, MIC and MI ensured transparent communication throughout the process, from issuing calls for participants to presenting national results, and continued to disseminate results afterwards. Irish CP representatives participated in a session audition of the national joint parliamentary committee on media as they prepare new media legislation, while the Slovenian participants presented their demands at an event attended by high-ranking officials of the Ministry of Culture, and the Czech members presented theirs in the Senate. In Austria, politicians and media representatives involved in reforming the media system responded to the presentation of the CPs' results at the Austrian Press Club. Finally, the resolutions of the four CPs were presented to MEPs in the European Parliament in Brussels.

Since the conclusion of the CPs, the WP6 partners have continued to share the results with stakeholders involved in media policy. They are also sharing the expertise they gained from implementing a deliberative, participatory citizens' process that supports democracy. To this end, the WP6 partners have participated in various conferences, publications and broadcasts, as detailed in the appendices. They also intend to develop further exploitation activities after the project's end, based on the experience of the CPs.

COMMIT, which is engaged in promoting media literacy and supporting free broadcasting in Austria, is planning to offer community media and adult education training, drawing inspiration from the format of the Citizens' Parliaments. Based on the theoretical framework on Media and Democracy (Carpentier and Wimmer, 2025) and the results from the Citizens' Parliament in Austria, COMMIT will develop a learning module on critical media literacy for adult education. COMMIT has also set up a project application to implement Citizens' Parliaments with local partners in rural areas in Austria. This project application has been submitted as a proposal for the call of Pro-European Values 2026 in Austria which is based on the EC-CERV-program.

Austrian CP members were invited twice to be discussants in a dialogue forum on the Austrian national broadcaster ORF, thus exploiting the expertise gained from participating in the CP. One delegate is currently involved in a development process at the Public Service broadcaster to bring in the outcomes of the CP-process for reform in public service media. Another CP member was invited by a member of the Austrian advisory board to present the results of the Austrian CP and their experience of the CP process in a university seminar in media and communication studies. Many CP members are also actively sharing the resolutions in their own contexts, thus actively contributing to dissemination and potential exploitation of the results.

At the national level, COMMIT got feedback from the media spokesperson and member of the National Council Klaus Seltenheim (Social Democrat Party) that he is motivated to invite delegates from the Austrian Citizens' Parliament to the national parliament to present their work and discuss the adopted CP-resolutions and to discuss a potential uptake in policy making. At the European level, COMMIT had two follow-up meetings in Brussels on 14.1.2026 – the day after the MeDeMAP-presentation event in the European Parliament – with SP-MEP Hannes Heide from the EP-CULT-Committee and with team members of Austrian MEP Lena Schilling and German MEP Erik Marquardt from the Green fraction to discuss concrete options to take up inspiration from the EP-resolutions for their work in the European Parliament.

Charles University (CU): The dissemination, impact and exploitation-oriented efforts by CU concern the academic, policy and societal levels:

Academia: At the levels of impact and exploitation, the academic activities carried out by CU, listed in Appendix 2, created opportunities for learning at both national and international levels. These activities enabled the sharing of knowledge and skills with the academic community on methodology, design, theory development, and analysis, with a focus on citizen parliaments and assemblies as tools for democratic enhancement. Exploitation activities will continue in 2026 through the organisation of seminars and workshops for the academic community. These will share knowledge on the design and organisation of citizen parliaments as participatory and deliberative tools for citizen engagement, as well as on the role of theory in supporting research in this area. For example, a seminar is planned for members of IAMCR (International Association for Media and Communication Research) in 2026.

Policy level: CU has broadly disseminated and presented the activities and outputs of the Czech Citizen Parliament to political stakeholders and policymakers in the Czech Republic, as well as to selected actors in the European Parliament and the European Commission, and beyond Europe. These activities, which have clear impact and exploitation dimensions, will continue after the project's formal completion, during 2026. Past activities, whose impact and exploitation dimensions extend into the present and future, include, for example:

- Roundtable at the Senate of the Czech Republic (05/06/2025): “Media for Democracy: Roundtable on Strengthening Media and Democracy in Czech Society” (Média pro demokracii: Kulatý stůl o posilování médií a demokracie v české společnosti). The roundtable involved representatives of the Czech Senate, media policy stakeholders, and Czech Citizen Parliament participants and organisers.
- Roundtable at the European Parliament (13/01/2026): “What do European citizens have to teach EU media policy?” (part of the session “Regulating Media for Future Democracies: Political and People’s Voice”). The roundtable involved participants from the Czech Citizen Parliament (together with participants from citizen parliaments in Austria, Ireland, and Slovenia), members of the European Parliament, and EU media policy stakeholders.
- Series of newsletters distributed to political and policy actors, media stakeholders, and civil society organisations in the Czech Republic during and after the operation of the Czech Citizen Parliament (March–June 2025), raising awareness of the citizen parliament model, its activities, and its outcomes.

Meetings with key stakeholders, promoting the Czech citizen parliament and its output to policy actors, included:

- Meeting with Monika Ladmanová, Head of the EC Representation in the Czech Republic, and collaborator Martin Pelc (18.6.2025);
- Meeting with David Březina, Eurodesk Coordinator for Ostrava (15.9.2025);
- Telephone meeting with Markéta Kopecká, Eurodesk worker in Brno (09/2025);
- Meeting with Klára Laurenčíková, Commissioner for Human Rights in Czechia (10 October 2025).

At the level of impact and exploitation, these activities increased awareness and visibility of the citizen parliament concept at the national level. This awareness-raising is particularly important in the Czech context, where citizen parliaments or assemblies are not well-known tools of citizen deliberation. In parallel, these activities enhanced the visibility of Czech citizens' demands at both national and European levels among key policymaking actors and institutions. The meetings with individual stakeholders are considered effective, as many agreed to include the Czech Citizen Parliament as an example of good practice in their presentations, dissemination activities and projects.

- Policy lab learning webinar: Nico Carpentier and Vaia Doudaki presented the Czech Citizen Parliament in a webinar titled "Citizens' Parliament: Lessons in Public Participation" (24 October 2025), organised by the Institute of Policy Studies at the National University of Singapore. The webinar was attended by approximately 90 public administration, civil society, and academic participants. At the exploitation level, the webinar created learning opportunities by enhancing participants' knowledge of methods, tools and skills, as well as of the conditions of possibility required to organise this type of participatory activities.
- Social media dissemination and exploitation: Further dissemination activities with a strong exploitation dimension include the creation of social media content by Johana Bázlerová, a prominent Czech influencer in the fields of politics and media (her Instagram channel *Jsem v obraze* has more than 200,000 followers). Bázlerová will disseminate the Czech Citizen Parliament's resolutions, increasing visibility of the citizen parliament and its outputs and reaching a broad range of political and media actors that are typically difficult to engage (content under preparation).

Societal level: Advisory Council: The Advisory Council for the Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy, consisting of representatives from 10 civil society and media-related organisations and associations, served as an important venue for dissemination and exploitation activities. The Advisory Council supported the recruitment of Citizen Parliament participants from diverse social groups by facilitating the circulation of the call for participants and strengthening links with civil society. Raising awareness of the citizen parliament in the Czech Republic – where such deliberative formats are not widely known – was a key exploitation-oriented activity, both during the recruitment phase and throughout the Citizen Parliament's operation and dissemination of its resolutions report.

In addition, the methodology and design of the Czech Citizen Parliament were shared with the Advisory Council for feedback and discussion, creating opportunities for mutual knowledge exchange. A dedicated meeting was organised with two representatives of the Platform for Citizen Assemblies (*Platforma pro občanská shromáždění*) (which was one of the Advisory

Council members) on 13 November 2024 to explore the applicability of the Czech Citizen Parliament's design in other contexts and projects, facilitating the exchange of experiences and good practices.

- Education and civic literacy: Another example of knowledge circulation and societal impact was the presentation of the Czech Citizen Parliament at the 2025 Annual Conference of the Association of Civics and Social Science Teachers (Občankáři) (25 August 2025, Prague), as a good practice in civic and media literacy.
- Further societal uptake: Moreover, individual parliamentarians have expressed interest in using the design and methodology of the Czech Citizen Parliament as a learning tool for new initiatives. For example, one parliamentarian working as an education manager for a library and digitalisation centre is planning to establish an “incubator for civic parliaments”, using the Czech Citizen Parliament's design and detailed script as a guiding framework.

Mary Immaculate College (MIC) has started to exploit the outcomes of the Citizens' Parliament through sharing the approach that was so successful with other researchers and academics and by following up on the resolutions of the citizens to ensure that they are implemented where possible. To this end, MIC has already shared their expertise with colleagues in Dublin City University (DCU) who then used what they had learned to organise “Citizens' Labs” as part of their work on the HORIZON funded project “Resilient Media for Democracy in the Digital Age” (ReMeD), Grant Agreement ID: ReMeD 101094742. The MIC team has been approached to provide similar help to Tallinn University. Vice-Rector for Development, Katrin Saks, who has requested this, will be in touch to organise the same format.

MIC will be following up with the politicians met at the local level in July, at the national level in November and with the five Irish MEPs met in Brussels in January to ensure that they follow through on their promises to consider how best they might implement some of the citizens' resolutions.

MIC is sharing both the methodology and the resolutions of the Citizens' Parliament with academics and students in the Limerick region on 25th February in MIC. This will be a four-hour, drop-in session for members of Limerick's academic community. There are three colleges: MIC, University of Limerick and Technological University of the Shannon in the city. Academics, researchers and students can meet the research team and ask questions. These may include political scientists, sociologists, students of journalism and media and communication studies but it is also anticipated that researchers who are interested in Participatory Action Research, in Citizen Parliaments and in the Art of Hosting as more experimental forms of research will be drawn to the event.

The resolutions of the Citizens' Parliament have been shared with the NUJ and with Media Literacy Ireland. MIC is planning to provide a workshop and a presentation to Craol, the community radio forum of Ireland at their national annual training event in the Autumn of 2026. MIC is available to offer a tailored version to both the NUJ and Media Literacy Ireland over the coming months.

Mirovni Institute (MI) is working on exploiting the CP outcomes in two ways: through the advancement of substantive policy demands, and through the promotion of the CP model itself

as a participatory instrument for media reform, particularly in the context of the expected comprehensive reform of public service broadcasting, RTV Slovenia. As the new media law entered the parliamentary adoption procedure in 2025, MI actively participated in parliamentary deliberations, notably within the National Assembly's Cultural Committee, where amendment proposals explicitly referenced the MeDeMAP research and the demands formulated by the Citizens' Parliament (CP).

In the final months of the project, in early 2026, the national election campaign ahead of the parliamentary elections scheduled for 22 March provides a strategic opportunity to advance the demands of the Citizens' Parliament and to disseminate the MeDeMAP research on participation in media and democracy. During this period, joint demands are articulated towards political parties within the framework of the broad informal civil society coalition Voice of the People. In the field of media policy, these joint demands were substantively grounded in the CP resolutions and required political parties to publicly position themselves on key policy issues.

Following the elections, the implementation of these commitments by elected parties and the new government will be systematically monitored. This will include commitments related to the CP demands for establishment of a unified media regulator, increased support for grassroots media, the introduction of a national media literacy programme, the appointment of a national media ombudsman, and the strengthening of participatory mechanisms for citizens in the development of media policy and regulation, notably through the use of the CP format.

4. Conclusion and recommendations

Based on the outcomes and the learnings from the process of the four Citizens' Parliaments in Austria, Czech Republic, Ireland and Slovenia, we are concluding with some core aspects and recommendations for future work of and with Citizens' Parliaments we want to highlight here.

Aligning Citizens' Parliaments with policy windows

To maximize impact, CPs should be strategically timed to coincide with moments of policy change, such as media law reforms, elections, or the formation of new governments. For instance, Slovenia's CP was particularly influential because it took place during the drafting of the country's Media Act, allowing citizen recommendations to be directly referenced in parliamentary debates. Similarly, in Austria, the presentation of CP resolutions at the Press Club Concordia sparked discussions among media policymakers and industry representatives. Policymakers and civil society organizations should proactively identify these opportunities and ensure that CPs are integrated into the policy-making timeline.

Inclusive and transparent processes

The effectiveness of a CP depends on its ability to include diverse voices and maintain transparency throughout the process. Recruitment efforts should target a broad cross-section of society, using community networks, local media, and civil society organizations to reach underrepresented groups. Additionally, documenting and publicly sharing the CP's methodology, discussions, and resolutions, as seen in the MeDeMAP blog and national reports, builds trust and allows others to replicate or adapt the process.

The dissemination of CP resolutions must be multi-faceted and targeted to ensure they reach the right audiences. This includes engagement at local, national and European level but also involving a wide range of partners such as public broadcasters, social media influencers and local media to amplify the message. Partnerships with media outlets and civil society networks are essential for broadening the reach of CP recommendations.

Knowledge for long-term impact

The value of CPs extends beyond their immediate resolutions; they also generate knowledge and expertise that can be used to strengthen democratic processes in the long term. As a consequence, local governments and civil society organizations but also researchers should be encouraged to adopt CPs as a regular tool for citizen engagement.

CP findings should be integrated into education by developing training modules and curricula on media literacy and participatory democracy to be used in adult education, schools, and community media training.

The implementation of CPs recommendations should be monitored, and political decision makers should be questioned about this in upcoming debates and election campaigns.

Common challenges to overcome

While CPs offer immense potential, they also risk to face challenges such as limited resources, low public awareness, and resistance from stakeholders. To address these challenges, broad partnerships are crucial. This should include collaboration with universities, media organizations, and funders to share the burden of organizing and promoting CPs.

CPs might better start at the local or regional level to demonstrate their value before scaling up. Austria's experience with regional CPs in Vorarlberg and Vienna might provide a useful model. Feedback from participants, stakeholders, and policymakers should be used to refine the CP process. Post-CP surveys and public discussions might help to identify areas for improvement.

The MeDeMAP Citizens' Parliaments have shown that citizens are not only capable of contributing meaningfully to media policy but that their involvement can lead to more democratic, inclusive, and responsive media systems. However, harnessing this potential requires commitment from all stakeholders, especially from policy makers, media organisations, civil society and academia.

Learnings for further research on and with Citizens' Parliaments

The MeDeMAP Citizens' Parliaments (CPs) offered a rich methodological framework for further research into how citizens envision and articulate their democratic imaginations and needs – especially in the context of media and public communication.

In future cases, it would make sense to explore the relationship between CP processes and broader democratic engagement. Future studies could investigate how participation in CPs influences citizens' long-term civic behaviour, such as their involvement in local advocacy, media literacy initiatives, or even formal political processes. Longitudinal research, tracking CP participants over time, could assess whether deliberative experiences foster a deeper sense of

democratic efficacy or trust in institutions. Furthermore, researchers might examine how the design of CPs (e.g., facilitation methods, diversity of participants, or use of digital tools) affects the depth and inclusivity of democratic imaginations expressed. For instance, comparing in-person and hybrid CP formats could shed light on which settings best encourage marginalized voices to articulate their needs, ensuring that future CPs are both representative and transformative.

Finally, research could focus on bridging the gap between citizen-generated evidence and policy action. While CPs produce valuable insights into democratic needs, their impact depends on how well these findings are translated into tangible reforms. Researchers could study the barriers and enablers of policy uptake, such as the role of advisory boards, media coverage, or partnerships with policymakers, in ensuring that citizen recommendations are heard and acted upon. In general, CPs should not be seen as isolated events but as part of a continuous feedback loop between citizens and institutions, where research can help to institutionalise their role as a vital tool for evidence-based democratic renewal.

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Appendix 1: Overview of the WP6 partners' communication activities

COMMIT (Austria) – Communication activities

Communication activities	Communication Channel	#	Link
Blog Posts on Austrian CP on Media & Democracy (in German)	COMMIT / MeDeMAP Blog/Austrian CP section	12	https://medemap.commit.at/buergerinnenrat/
Newsletters: Reporting on the progress of the Austrian CP on media and democracy	COMMIT Newsletter	6	
Podcasts: Reporting on Austrian CP and its results	COMMIT Podcast "COMMITed" on 11.6.24, 14.7.25	3	https://cba.media/666488 , https://cba.media/722749 and https://cba.media/753764
Social media posts. Information on CP Austria Media and Democracy	COMMIT LinkedIn, Bluesky, Mastodon, Facebook	60	
Flyers: Austrian Citizen Parliament Media & Democracy	COMMIT. Print Materials. Flyers shared with multipliers.	2	
National Report: CP Austria on Media and Democracy as leaflet/poster and pdf document	COMMIT. Report on Austrian CP's results. Printed and online. Shared with multipliers and stakeholders.	1	https://www.commit.at/fileadmin/Materialien/MeDeMap/COMMIT_CPA-Report_A4_EN.pdf
Press releases on Austrian CP	COMMIT partners: Vienna City News agency: 19.12.24 and 26.5.25	2	https://www.ots.at/presseaussendung/OTS_20241219_OTS0128/demokratie-braucht-starke-medien-buergerinnen-bringen-ihre-perspektiven-ein https://www.ots.at/presseaussendung/OTS_20250526_OTS0141/demokratie-medien-und-das-vertrauen
APA News agency article on the results of Austrian CP	APA Austrian Press Agency News (25.6.25)	1	https://www.msn.com/de-at/nachrichten/kultur/b%C3%BCrgerinnenrat-richtet-forderungen-an-medien-und-politik/ar-AA1HpiOe
Print media campaign: print articles on Austrian CP	Der Standard (14.2.25), Vienna city media "Mein Wien" 01/2025, Vienna city Bezirksblatt (twice): Newsletter plus print (15.2.25), Skug-Magazin (online), Archipel	7	Der Standard https://www.derstandard.at/story/3000000257394/buergerinnenrat-ueber-medien-und-demokratie-sucht-noch-buergerinnen , Skug Magazine https://skug.at/medien-demokratie-und-darkwave/

Radio campaign: Reports & interviews on Radio on the Austrian CP	Radio Orange Mordor (24.1.25), Freies Radio Freistadt Kulturmix & Radio FRO Frozine (18.2.25), Radio Orange ANDI 335 (30.5.25),	7	Radio Orange Mordor https://cba.media/700650 , Freies Radio Freistadt Kulturmix https://cba.media/697678 , Radio FRO Frozine https://cba.media/697761 , Radio Orange ANDI https://o94.at/programm/sendung/id/2384976
TV report on the national presentation of CP results	OKTO TV (community TV)	1	https://www.okto.tv/de/sendereihe/jukebox/video/6899b26e0f04c/forderungen-des-burger-innenrates-medien-und-demokratie-an-medien-politik-und-bildung
Public discussions on participatory democracy	Skug Salon Vienna (14.3.25)	1	https://skug.at/medien-demokratie-und-darkwave/

COMMIT – Call for Participants: Postcard

CU (Czech Republic) – Communication activities

For up-to-date information, see <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/outputs/>

Blog posts on WP6 MeDeMAP Blog

- 7 Blog Posts on Czech CP on COMMIT-WP6 MeDeMAP Blog
<https://medemap.commit.at/medemap-blog/>

Media coverage (4 articles, 1 interview)

- Radio Interview. *V Česku proběhl první Občanský parlament. Přinesl paletu návrhů na proměnu českých médií.* 20.06.2025 Archive: <https://archive.ph/HviQW>
- Regionalní noviny reported on the presentation of the results of the first Citizens' Parliament on media and democracy, held in the Senate. *Regionální noviny informovaly o prezentaci výsledků prvního Občanského parlamentu o médiích a demokracii, která se konala v Senátu v rámci evropského projektu MeDeMAP.* 08.06.2025 Archive: archive.ph/g4Eg7
- Article about the Citizens' Parliament in the Friday-Sunday edition of Deník N. *Článek o Občanském parlamentu vyšel v pátečně-nedělním vydání Deníku N.* 20-22. 12.2024. <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/IV-V.pdf>
- Article about the Citizens' Parliament on the website of the Deník N. *Článek o Občanském parlamentu byl zveřejněn na stránkách Deníku N.* 17. 12.2024 Archive: <https://archive.ph/ey1QC>
- Article in the magazine Doba seniorů, published by the Czech Council of Senior Citizens about the CP. *Časopis Doba seniorů, který vydává Rada českých seniorů, vydal článek informující o občanském parlamentu o médiích a demokracii.* December 2024 Archive: https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/2_Doba-senioru-Senior-Times_p.-5.pdf

Press releases

- Press release on Roundtable organized in the Senate of the Czech Republic to present the results of the CP. *První občanský parlament o médiích a demokracii v Česku má výsledky. Zazněly na kulatém stole v Senátu PČR.* 05.06.2025 Archive: <https://archive.ph/vYFw8>
- Press release on Media experts presenting the results of the CP. *Mediální odborníci představili v Senátu výsledky prvního občanského parlamentu o médiích a demokracii v Česku.* 05.06.2025 Archive: <https://archive.ph/ZxrQ6>
- The press release and the call for participants for the Citizens' Parliament have been published in nášLiberec. *Tisková zpráva a výzva pro účastníky Občanského parlamentu byly zveřejněny v našemLiberci.* 09.12.2024 Archive: <https://archive.ph/97hZ0>
- Press release published on the website of the Council of Senior Citizens of the Czech Republic. *Tisková zpráva zveřejněná na webových stránkách Rady seniorů ČR.* 04.11.2024 Archive: <https://archive.ph/jhTR0>
- Press release with open call and invitations to the Citizens' Parliament available on the Alarm podcasts. *Deník Alarm publikoval tiskovou zprávu s otevřenou výzvou a pozvánky do občanského parlamentu jsou ke slyšení v podcastech Alarmu.* 5. 11.2024. Archive: <https://archive.ph/tKG9w>

- Press release on the Citizens' Parliament. *Tisková zpráva: Zveřejnili jsme tiskovou zprávu k Občanskému parlamentu. Praha. 26 August 2024.*

Media Campaign (advertisement)

- Advertisement for the Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy in the Czech Republic published in the dobrovolnik.cz website. *Na stránkách voluntenik.cz byla zveřejněna reklama na Občanský parlament o médiích a demokracii v České republice. 18.12.2024* Archive: <https://archive.ph/kJ23l>
- Advertisement in the Respekt weekly published with call for the Citizen's Parliament. *Týdeník Respekt otiskl leták s otevřenou výzvou. 02-08.12.2024* Archive: https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/3_Respekt_49_p.-69.pdf
- Banners published in The Alarm newspaper for the recruitment campaign for the CP. *V novinách Alarm jsou zveřejněny bannery k náborové kampani do Občanského parlamentu pro média a demokracii. November 2024*
- Podcast inviting citizens to get involved in the citizens' parliament. *V podcastu byli občané vyzváni, aby se zapojili do činnosti občanského parlamentu. November 2024*
- The Alarm newspaper published a press release with an open call and invitations to the Citizens' Parliament are available on the Alarm podcasts. *Náborová kampaň do občanského parlamentu o médiích a demokracii začala. Deník Alarm publikoval tiskovou zprávu s otevřenou výzvou a pozvánky do občanského parlamentu jsou ke slyšení v podcastech Alarmu. November 2024*

Social Media Campaign

- Short video about the Citizens' Parliament posted on the Institute of Communication Studies and Journalism's Instagram account. *Krátké video na Instagramu. Na instagramovém účtu Institutu komunikačních studií a žurnalistiky bylo zveřejněno krátké video o Občanském parlamentu. 11.10.2024* Archive: <https://archive.ph/ggHj5>
- Call for volunteers to participate in the Citizens' Parliament posted on the ICSJ Instagram account. *Na instagramovém účtu IKSŽ byla zveřejněna výzva pro dobrovolníky, kteří se chtějí podílet na činnosti Občanského parlamentu. 11.09.2024* Archive: <https://archive.ph/3UWiR>
- Call for Participants On Website of ICSJ. *Pozvánka k účasti v Českém občanském parlamentu pro média a demokracii byla zveřejněna na webových stránkách IKSŽ. 28.05.2024* Archive: <https://archive.ph/zMtjh>

Blog Post on MeDeMAP Media Mapping Blog

- "Premature conclusions? What (we think) we know about European democracy and media" by Kirill Filimonov 31.05.2024. Archive: <https://archive.ph/PwPez>
- "The State of Community Media in the Czech Republic", by Karolína Šimková, 7.3.2024. <https://media.medemap.eu/2024/03/07/the-state-of-community-media-in-the-czech-republic/>

Leaflets

- Leaflets with the open call published in regional media: the Kroměříž deník, the Olomouc deník, the Zlín deník and the Přerov deník. *Letáky s otevřenou výzvou vyšly v regionálních*

médiích: v Kroměřížském deníku, Olomouckém deníku, Zlínském deníku a Přerovském deníku.
18.11.2024 Archive: https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/1_18_11_2024_VM_OLOM_1_6df061d533.pdf

- Call for Participants: Leaflet. *Právě jsme zveřejnili leták k občanskému parlamentu o médiích a demokracii. Otevřená výzva platí nejen pro studující, ale také pro jejich blízké a rodiny.*
<https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Flyer.jpg>

CU - Call for Participants: Leaflet

**OBČANÉ
ROZHODUJÍ
O MÉDIÍCH**

**Zapojte se do prvního
občanského parlamentu
o médiích a demokracii
v Česku.**

Kdy: březen–červen 2025
Kde: Praha, Brno, Olomouc

Více informací:
medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/op

**Pokud se chcete
zapojit, napište na:**
milos.hroch@fsv.cuni.cz

MIC (Ireland) – Communication activities

For up-to-date information, see <https://www.mic.ul.ie/MeDeMap?index=4>

Blog posts on WP6 MeDeMAP Blog

6 Blog Posts on Irish CP on COMMIT-WP6 MeDeMAP Blog <https://medemap.commit.at/medemap-blog/>

MeDeMAP Video

03.2025 <https://www.mic.ul.ie/MeDeMap?index=4>

Media coverage

4 radio and TV interviews

- Near fm. MeDeMap. 08.04 2025. <https://listenagain.org/?p=55092>
- RTÉ Raidió na Gaeltachta 25.01.24. <https://www.rte.ie/radio/podcasts/22347258-dr-rosemary-day-ceannasai-roinn-leinn-na-mean/>
- RTE Raidió na Gaeltachta 4.4.25. <https://www.rte.ie/radio/rnag/adhmhaidin/2025/0404/1505846-adhmhaidin-de-haoine-4-aibrean-2025/>
- National Television – Oireachtas TV. Video of the debate of the Joint Committee on Arts, Media, Communications, Culture and Sport (starting at 1:40:00): <https://www.oireachtas.ie/en/oireachtas-tv/video-archive/committees/?datePeriod=dates&fromDate=05%2F11%2F2025&toDate=05%2F11%2F2025&committee=%2Fen%2Fcommittees%2F34%2Farts-media-communications-culture-and-sport%2F>
- Dublin City Community TV, 22.1.2026

Articles in print media

- Article in Live95. Calls for 'Media Literacy' to be taught in school. 7 April 2025. <https://www.live95fm.ie/news/live95-news/calls-for-media-literacy-to-be-taught-in-school/>
- Article in the Limerick Leader. Citizens' parliament to meet Limerick as part of European project. 07 Mar 2025. <https://www.limerickleader.ie/news/politics/1745746/citizens-parliament-to-meet-limerick-as-part-of-european-project.html>
- Article in the Limerick Leader. Citizens' parliament is dissolved after final sitting in Limerick. 18 May 2025. <https://www.limerickleader.ie/news/politics/1802032/citizens-parliament-is-dissolved-after-final-sitting-in-limerick.html>
- Magazine article in Changing Ireland: Summer 2024 <https://www.changingireland.ie/digital-magazine-archive/>
- 2 Press releases

Podcasts

- Interview Live95 Limerick. MIC Professor on the links Between Social Media and Democracy. 10.036.2025. <https://www.mic.ul.ie/MeDeMap?index=4>
- Interview Live95 Limerick. Update on the Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy in Limerick. 9.05.2025. <https://www.mic.ul.ie/MeDeMap?index=4>

Blog posts on MIC website

- Update on Citizen's Parliament Ireland. 10 November 2025. <https://www.mic.ul.ie/mic-insights/medemap-november-update-on-citizens-parliament-ireland>

- Irish National Citizens' Parliament present at the July meeting of Limerick City and County Council. 18 July 2025. <https://www.mic.ul.ie/mic-insights/irish-national-citizens-parliament-present-at-the-july-meeting-of-limerick-city-and>
- Irish National Citizens' Parliament Finishes on a High Note! <https://www.mic.ul.ie/mic-insights/irish-national-citizens-parliament-finishes-on-a-high-note>
- Representation in the Media - Of All the People, By All the People. 6 May 2025. <https://www.mic.ul.ie/mic-insights/representation-in-the-media-of-all-the-people-by-all-the-people>
- Citizens Gather at MIC for Citizens' Parliaments to shape the future of media and democracy. 28 Mar 2025. <https://www.mic.ul.ie/news/2025/citizens-gather-at-mic-for-citizens-parliaments-to-shape-the-future-of-media-and-democracy>
- Media and Democracy – Citizens have their say. 19 March 2025. <https://www.mic.ul.ie/mic-insights/media-and-democracy-citizens-have-their-say>

MIC- Call for Participants: Poster

HAVE YOUR VOICE HEARD and RECEIVE €400 in VOUCHERS for 4 Days Participation as a thank you!

(must be available to attend for all four days and be aged 18 +)

Join us to discuss how the media can support democracy
 Make resolutions that will be heard in Limerick, Dáil Éireann
 and Europe

Meet and talk with other interested people
 (lunch etc. provided)

Email MeDeMap@mic.ul.ie to register your interest and find out more

Funded by
the European Union

MI (Slovenia) – Communication activities

Communication activities	Communication Channel	#	Link
Post (news) on Peace Institute website (Slovenian and English)	Peace Institute website	24	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/?s=medemap
Peace Institute subpage dedicated to CP	CP subpage, Peace Institute website	1	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/mediji-demokracija/
Social media post	Facebook and Instagram		https://www.facebook.com/mirovni.institut.si ; https://www.instagram.com/mirovni_institut/
Newsletter (public call for participation on CP)	Newsletter	1	Sent to more than 1.500 e-mails.
Newsletter (CP resolutions)	Newsletter	1	Sent to more than 1.500 e-mails.
Press release (CP resolutions)	Individual e-mails	1	Sent to 150 individual e-mails.
Blog posts on COMMIT website	Blog posts	7	-
Public call for participation	Media outlet Oštro	1	https://www.ostro.si/si/novice/vabilo-na-zbore-obcanov-o-medijih-in-demokraciji
Public call for participation	Media outlet Mladina	1	https://www.mladina.si/238242/odlocevalcem-posljite-svoje-predloge-o-medijih-in-demokraciji/
Print flyers (call for participation on CP)	Distributed in public spaces (libraries, faculties, shops, etc.)	100	
Print posters (call for participation on CP)	Distributed in public spaces (libraries, faculties, shops, etc.)	100	-
Print resolutions (Slovenian)	Public presentation, events, conferences	200	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/zbor-obcanov_web.pdf
Print resolution (English)	International events and conferences	30	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/ANG_zahteve-zbora_booklet-web.pdf
Infographics with resolutions	CP subpage, Peace Institute website	3	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/mediji-demokracija/

MI- Call for Participants: Poster

KJE?
Ljubljana

KDAJ?
15. marec,
29. marec,
12. april,
10. maj.

10:00-16:00

**ŽELITE SODELOVATI
NA ZBORU OBČANK_OV
O MEDIJIH
IN DEMOKRACIJI?**

OBVEZNA PRIJAVA
na povezavi QR kode (levo)
ali preko e-pošte:
tjasa.turnsek@
mirovni-institut.si

prijave zbiramo
do 20. 2. 2025

**VEČ O ZBORU
OBČANK_OV**
najdete na povezavi
QR kode (desno)
in na spletni strani
www.mirovni-institut.si
(projekt MeDeMAP)

MEDEMAP Mirovni inštitut

Funded by
the European Union

Financirna Evropska unija. Stališča in mnenja, izražena v tem besedilu, so izključna odgovornost avtorjev, ic in ne odražajo nujno stališč Evropske unije ali Evropske izvajalske agencije za raziskave. Na Evropska unija niš agencija za njih ne odgovarjate.

ŽELITE SODELOVATI NA ZBORU OBČANK_OV O MEDIJIH IN DEMOKRACIJI?

Med marcem in junijem 2025 bo Mirovni inštitut organiziral **zbor občank_ov o medijih in demokraciji**.

Če vas zanima obravnavana tema in udeležba, vas vabimo, da se prijavite.

Zbor občank_ov bo potekal ob sobotah na **štirih zaporednih srečanjih v Ljubljani**, okvimo med 10. in 16. uro v teh dneh:

- sobota, **15. marec**,
- sobota, **29. marec**,
- sobota, **12. april**,
- sobota, **10. maj**.

Izbrali bomo **20 udeleženk_cev**, ki bodo po sestavi odražali raznoličnost prebivalstva glede na spol, starost, izobrazbo in druge demografske kazalce.

Obvezno je, da se izbrani kandidati_ke udeležijo vseh štirih srečanj.

Na srečanjih bo poskrbljeno za prigrizke in kosilo, predvideno je tudi simbolično denarno nadomestilo za udeležbo.

Zbor občank_ov je del evropskega znanstveno-raziskovalnega projekta o medijih in demokraciji (MeDeMAP).

Če vas zanima sodelovanje na zboru občank_ov o medijih in demokraciji, se prijavite preko QR kode ali nam pišite na naslov: tjasa.turnsek@mirovni-institut.si. **Prijave zbiramo do 20. 2. 2025.**

OBVEZNA PRIJAVA
na povezavi QR kode (levo)
ali preko e-pošte:
tjasa.turnsek@
mirovni-institut.si

prijave zbiramo
do 20. 2. 2025

**VEČ O ZBORU
OBČANK_OV**
najdete na povezavi
QR kode (levo)
in na spletni strani
www.mirovni-institut.si
(projekt MeDeMAP)

Appendix 2: Overview of the WP6 partners' dissemination activities

COMMIT (Austria) – Dissemination activities

Dissemination activities	What?	Audience	Place & Time	Link
"Learning democracy" through participation in the citizens' parliaments on media and democracy in Austria, the Czech Republic, Ireland and Slovenia" Policy paper	Academic article	Research	MedienJournal, University of Klagenfurt, Austria (<i>in progress</i>)	https://netlibrary.aau.at/medienjournal
Chapter on how the procedure of Citizen Parliaments is implemented as a qualitative research method	Academic Handbook Chapter	Research	Handbook of qualitative research in communication science edited by Jeffrey Wimmer (<i>in progress</i>)	
Medien- und Demokratiebildung im Bürger*innenrat Medien und Demokratie	Article	Research & NGOs in Adult education/ civic education	Die Österreichische Volkshochschule 01.11.2025	https://magazin.vhs.or.at/magazin/2025-2/285-herbstwinter-2025/bildungsthemen/medien-und-demokratiebildung-im-buergerinnenrat-medien-und-demokratie/
Österreich: Bürger-innenräte, Medien und Demokratie / Autriche, médias: Conseils citoyens, médias et démocratie	Article	European institutions & NGOs in Adult education/ civic education/ Media	European Civic Forum. 9.9.2025 (German) & 19.10.2025 (French)	https://forumcivique.org/artikel/oesterreich-buergerinnenraete-medien-und-demokratie/ & https://forumcivique.org/fr/artikel/oesterreich-buergerinnenraete-medien-und-demokratie/
Interview Ernest Taqi (OEAW) on European media landscape	Blog article	Research, EU institutions	MeDeMAP/ The Media Mapping Blog, 18.05.2025	https://media.medemap.eu/2025/05/18/a-functioning-democracy-needs-media-as-platforms-for-public-discourse/
Web article: CPs as democracy education on Adult Education	Blog article	EU institutions, Research & NGOs in Adult education/ civic education	European Adult Education Platform EPAL, 19.03.2025 (German) and 28.03.2025 (English)	https://epale.ec.europa.eu/en/blog/citizens-parliaments-participatory-learning-spaces-democracy-education
Web article on strengthening democratic participation through CPs	Blog article	Austrian institutions & NGOs in Adult education/ civic education, Research	Austrian Ministry of Education Website, 08.01.2026	https://erwachsenenbildung.at/aktuell/nachrichten/20747-partizipation-in-demokratien-staerken-das-spiel-mit-den-gefuehlen.php

"Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy: Citizens shaping the future of media" on Website Vienna European Capital of Democracy	Blog article	National authorities, Local authorities, Civil society, Research, Citizens	Website Vienna European Capital of Democracy, 13.9.2025	https://demokratiehauptstadt.wien.gv.at/buergerinnenrat-medien-und-demokratie
Presentation of CP process & results in festival "doing democracy" (Poster and oral presentation)	Conference	National authorities, Local authorities, Civil society, Citizens	Dramatiker-festival "Doing Democracy", Graz, 12.06.2025	https://erwachsenenbildung.at/aktuell/nachrichten/20336-demokratie-auf-die-buehne-bringen.php
Presentation of CP National Report and resolutions in Vienna (Press Club Concordia)	Conference	EU institutions, Research communities, International organisation	Round table at Press Club Concordia, Vienna, 25.06.2025	https://medemap.commit.at/the-austrian-citizens-parliament-on-media-and-democracy-presents-its-demands/
Presentation CP process & results in Symposium für politische Bildung organised by Region Upper Austria & Ars Electronica	Conference	Austrian institutions & NGOs in Adult education/ civic education	Symposium Ars Electronica, Linz, Austria, 3.9.25	https://ph-ooe.at/politische-bildung-2025
Round table "citizens' parliaments as a democratic innovation", organised by COMMIT	Conference	National authorities, Local authorities, Civil society, Research, Citizens	MeDeMAP Round Table, University of St. Pölten, Austria, 24.9.25	https://medemap.commit.at/citizens-parliaments-as-a-democratic-innovation-roundtable-at-the-final-medemap-project-meeting/
Presentation CP process & results in Conference on Democracy & Rights, EU/Fundamental Rights Agency	Conference	EU institutions, Research communities, International organisation	University of Copenhagen, 6.-7. 11.2025	https://www.nyteuropa.dk/democracy-rights-conference
Discussion & presentation of CP's results and its potential for adult education	Conference	Multipliers and managers in adult education	Adult Education Centre Vienna, 11.12.2025	-
Stand in closure event, Vienna European Capital of Democracy organised by City of Vienna	Project presentation	Local and national authorities, NGOs, Citizens	Vienna, closure Vienna European Capital of Democracy, 18.11.25	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/community-medieninstitut_gestern-%C3%BCbergab-wien-den-titel-europ%C3%A4ische-activity-7396927021643218944-J177?originalSubdomain=de
Deliverable 6.4. Report: Future roadmap for European media and democracy	MeDeMAP Deliverable	Research, European and national institutions, civil society	SEDLACZEK, ANDREA, HELMUT, PEISSL, MARTIN, ANDREAS, DOUDAKI, VAIA HROCH, MILOŠ, ŠANDA, ŠTĚPÁN, MONNOT, LAURENCE, CUSH, KATHY, DAY, ROSEMARY,	

			MCINERNEY, JUDE, ŠRAMEL ČEBULAR, LORI, TURNŠEK TJAŠA, & PETKOVIĆ, BRANKICA (2026). Report: Future roadmap for European media and democracy. MeDeMAP Deliverable 6.4. (in progress)	
Deliverable 6.3. Blog on Citizens' Parliaments	MeDeMAP Deliverable	Research, European and national institutions, civil society	MONNOT, LAURENCE, & SEDLACZEK, ANDREA, with contributions from PEISSL, HELMUT, DOUDAKI, VAIA, HROCH, MILOŠ, CARPENTIER, NICO, MCINERNEY, JUDE, DAY, ROSEMARY, ŠRAMEL ČEBULAR, LORI, & PETKOVIĆ, BRANKICA (2025). Blog on Citizens' Parliaments. MeDeMAP Deliverable 6.3, 28.02.2025.	https://www.medemap.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/09/MeDeMAP-Deliverable-6.3_V1.0.pdf
Deliverable 6.2. Design of Citizens' Parliaments.	MeDeMAP Deliverable	Research, European and national institutions, civil society	MONNOT, LAURENCE, SEDLACZEK, ANDREA, PEISSL, HELMUT, CARPENTIER, NICO, DOUDAKI, VAIA, SEETHALER, JOSEF, DAY, ROSEMARY, & PETKOVIĆ, BRANKICA (2025). Design of Citizens' Parliaments. MeDeMAP Deliverable 6.2. 28.02.2025.	https://www.medemap.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/MeDeMAP-Deliverable-6.2_V1.0.pdf
Deliverable 6.1. Research Report on Successful Practice of Policy Development with Citizens' Parliaments in Europe	MeDeMAP Deliverable	Research, European and national institutions, civil society	MONNOT, LAURENCE, with contributions from PEISSL, HELMUT, SEDLACZEK, ANDREA, DAY, ROSEMARY, HROCH, MILOŠ, & PETKOVIĆ, BRANKICA (2025). Research Report on Successful practice of policy development with Citizens'	https://www.medemap.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/MeDeMAP-Deliverable-6.1_V1.0.pdf

			Parliaments in Europe. MeDeMAP Deliverable 6.1. 13.01.2025	
National Report CP Austria Media & Democracy with resolutions as PDF (in German)	Report	National authorities, Regional authorities, Local authorities, Civil society, Citizens	Available to download online from repository and distributed via mailing lists, blogs and social media as of 25.06.2025	https://www.commit.at/fileadmin/Materialien/MeDeMap/Buergerinnenrat-Medien-Demokratie_Bericht-A4_web.pdf
National Report CP Austria Media & Democracy with resolutions as PDF (in English)	Report	Austrian institutions & NGOs in Adult education/ civic education, Research	Available to download online from repository and distributed via mailing lists, blogs and social media as of 15.7.2025	https://www.commit.at/fileadmin/Materialien/MeDeMap/COMMIT_CPA-Report_A4_EN.pdf

COMMIT – Resolutions report (EN)

The Austrian Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy

The Resolutions

Democracy is the framework for living together in our diverse society. To actively participate in democracy, we need media that provide us with the best possible support. Media should provide trustworthy information, fulfil a control function vis-à-vis those exercising power, support social debates and exchange, represent social diversity and support the democratic participation of all citizens. A strong democracy therefore requires diverse media that fulfil the democratic, social and cultural needs of citizens. If media diversity and media quality are threatened, our democracy is also threatened.

Our resolutions are demands and suggestions aimed at media representatives, media and education policy makers and educational organisations – at local, regional, national and European level.

The results of our deliberations are based on an intensive discussion on the relationship between media and democracy and on helpful inputs from research and media practice. The fundamental question was: "What needs to change in order for the media to support democracy in the best possible way?"

Facilitator Ruth Pöschel shows the path from the idea to the final resolution.

The path through the Citizens' Parliament

The Austrian Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy met in Vienna from March to May 2020. On four Saturdays, 20 citizens discussed their demands on the media and adopted 10 resolutions aimed at strengthening the media's role in fostering a thriving democracy.

Vol. 12 March 2020: Introduction Media and Democracy
Sat. 4 April 2020

Media systems and media regulation
Sat. 18 April 2020

Participation in and through the media
Sat. 17 May 2020

Representation in the media

Each session began with introductory presentations from experts from research and the media, a table of which citizens identified key issues. From session 2 onwards, citizens drafted resolutions in four committees, which were then jointly adopted in plenary.

The resolutions appeal to decision makers in politics, the media, and education for support of diverse media that promote democracy.

Ensuring the quality of media content

We address: the Austrian Federal Ministry for Housing, Arts, Culture, Media and Sport (BMLRTMS)

- **1: Indicator-based media funding:** Media funding should be linked to scientifically validated indicators measuring the promotion of democratic participation of citizens in the media and their evaluation. To this end, we call for the commissioning of a scientific study to define indicators that capture the participation of the population in the media as part of media quality.
- **2: Strengthening the diversity of content:** In the interests of a broader representation of topics, media funding should be linked to the obligation for the media to maintain a predefined proportion of 'minority topics' in their overall volume of content.
- **3: Media education through media funding:** If media education is seen as training in the critical consumption of different media, all forms of media funding should be linked to mandatory contributions to media education.
- **4: Funding for journalist training:** Funding for journalist training should be expanded.
- **5: Funding of quality journalism:** We call for a cap on advertisements from public funds. Public money should be used more for the targeted, transparent and independent funding of quality journalism.
- **6: Promotion of quality journalism by the Austrian Press Council:** Press funding should be linked to membership in the Austrian Press Council.
- **7: Safeguarding quality journalism through the Austrian Press Council:** The Austrian Press Council should be given powers to impose legal and financial cautions.
- **8: Restored funding for free daily newspapers:** Free daily newspapers that do not practice quality journalism should not receive any funding.
- **9: Funding for community media:** Access to funding for non-commercial community media should be made easier.
- **10: Funding for umbrella organizations of community media:** Funding for umbrella organizations of community media should be expanded so that they can support communities in the production of content.
- **11: Transparency in the allocation of media funding:** We call for the expansion of Koinvo Austria's financial and human resources as an independent media authority. Funding decisions should be shifted from the Austrian Regulatory Authority for Broadcasting and Telecommunications, RTR GmbH, to Koinvo Austria.
- **12: Independence in decisions on media funding:** Decisions on public funding for media should be made by independent expert advisory boards.
- **13: Strengthening representation in funding advisory boards:** Members of funding advisory boards should be politically independent and professionally competent. The composition of the boards should take into account representation with regard to diversity characteristics, in particular age, gender, sexual orientation, origin, religion, etc.

The organising team

The Austrian Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy was organised by the Community Media Institute COMMIT in Vienna as part of the EU funded research project MeDvMAP. Financial support was provided by the ESFTE Foundation, the European Capital of Democracy Vienna 2020, the Austrian Regulatory Authority for Broadcasting and Telecommunications (RTR), and the European Civic Forum. The Vienna Adult Education Centre hosted the meetings.

COMMIT project team: Helmut Pöschel (coordinator), Lucretia Kersch (organisation and documentation), Andrea Seifried (communication and research), Laura Steiner (research assistant)

Facilitator: Ruth Pöschel Consulting (former facilitator at Ruth Pöschel, Markus Glatthard, Rupert Reuber)
Graphic: Ines Frey, Daniela Ertl and Verena Heidegger

The advisory board

An honorary advisory body, the board provided guidance and support throughout the process, from the call for citizens, the selection of experts to the dissemination of results.

The members of the advisory board are: Ruth Glaser (Chairman of Labour Union), Peter Henning (University of Vienna), Stefan Jurek (Vienna Adult Education Centre), Wolfgang Reiner (Vienna City Hall Library), Wilfried Stroh (Austrian Press Club), Stefan Tschir (Austrian Economic Chamber), and a member of the Austrian Press Council.

The EU research project MeDvMAP

The MeDvMAP (Mapping Media for Future Democracies) research project, funded by the European Union's "Horizon Europe" programme, provides the foundation for the Austrian Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy. Under the leadership of the Austrian Academy of Sciences (OAW), partners in ten EU countries are investigating the relationship between media and democracy, as well as citizens' demands for greater participation.

As part of the project, citizens' parliaments on media and democracy were held in parallel in Austria, Ireland, Slovenia, and the Czech Republic, as well as online in Germany. The results of all citizens' parliaments will be generalisable. Results in early 2020.

CU (Czech Republic) – Dissemination activities

For up-to-date information, see <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/outputs/>

Resolution reports in English and in Czech <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/op/>

Infographics <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/op/news/>

Infographic 1: Czech Citizen Parliament Resolutions

* pdf English: https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/wp-content/uploads/2025/12/CP-Infographics-EN_1.pdf

* pdf Czech: https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/wp-content/uploads/2025/12/OP_Infografika_CZ.pdf

* webpage English: <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/czech-cp-on-media-and-democracy/>

* webpage Czech: <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/cesky-obcansky-parlament/>

Infographic 2: Czech Citizen Parliament Resolutions on Community Media

* pdf English: https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/wp-content/uploads/2025/12/CP-Infographics-EN_2.pdf

* pdf Czech: https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/wp-content/uploads/2025/12/OP_Infografika_CZ_2.pdf

* webpage English: <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/resolutions-about-community-media>

* webpage Czech: <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/usneseni-o-komunitnich-mediich/>

Infographic 3: Czech Citizen Parliament Resolutions on Media and Information Literacy

* pdf English: https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/wp-content/uploads/2025/12/CP-Infographics-EN_3.pdf

* pdf Czech: https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/wp-content/uploads/2025/12/OP_Infografika_CZ_1.pdf

* webpage English: <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/resolutions-about-media-and-information-literacy/>

* webpage Czech: <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/usneseni-o-medialni-a-informacni-gramotnosti/>

MeDeMAP deliverable

PAR, Citizens' Parliaments & The Possible Paths of PAR-ification: A Literature Review. HROCH, MILOŠ (2024). PAR, Citizens' Parliaments & the Possible Paths of PAR-ification: A Literature Review. Prague: CULCORC. https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/MeDeMAP_PAR-CP-literature-review_working-paper.pdf

Publications on citizens' parliament <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/outputs/>

Culture and Communication Research Centre (2025). Resolutions Report by the Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy. Prague: CULCORC. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15692097>

Culture and Communication Research Centre (2025). Zpráva o rezolucích Občanského parlamentu o médiích a demokracii v ČR. Prague: CULCORC.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15647877>

Conferences, roundtables and seminars related to the citizens' parliaments

<https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/outputs/>

Seminar. The Czech Citizen Parliament: Analysing Media Change, Participation, and Democracy. 28.01.2026, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic.

<https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/events/>

CARPENTIER, NICO (2026) "Knowledge and Participation: From data fetishism and disinformation to participatory knowledge construction", presentation in *The Czech Citizen Parliament: Analysing Media Change, Participation, and Democracy* (28.01.2026, Charles University, Prague)

DOUDAKI, VAIA, (2026) "Constructions of democracy in the Czech citizen parliament", presentation in *The Czech Citizen Parliament: Analysing Media Change, Participation, and Democracy* (28.01.2026, Charles University, Prague)

WIMMER, JEFFREY (2026) "Games with frontiers: On performance, playfulness, and citizen parliaments", presentation in *The Czech Citizen Parliament: Analysing Media Change, Participation, and Democracy* (28.01.2026, Charles University, Prague)

HROCH, MILOS, ŠANDA, ŠTĚPÁN (2026) "Consensus and Dissensus on Media's Democratic Roles: The case of the Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy", presentation in *The Czech Citizen Parliament: Analysing Media Change, Participation, and Democracy* (28.01.2026, Charles University, Prague)

CARPENTIER, NICO & DOUDAKI, VAIA (2026) "*Transforming the Audience into a Political Actor: The Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy*. Beyond the Audience: Rethinking Participation and Power in the Age of Data Capitalism Conference, IULM, Rome, Italy (15-16 January 2026)

CARPENTIER, NICO, Lecture, "Research as intervention: The example of the Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy", PhD away days, Patejdlova Bouda, Czech Republic (5 December 2025). <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/outputs/>

Roundtable. Democracy and Media in Europe: Emerging Challenges. 13.11.2025 Uppsala Universitet. <https://www.uu.se/en/department/informatics-and-media/events/archive/2025-11-13-roundtable-democracy-and-media-in-europe-emerging-challenges>

Webinar. Citizens' Parliament: Lessons in Public Participation. 24.10.2025

<https://archive.ph/nvCck>

Roundtable. Imagining New Relations for Media and Democracy: Beyond Defeatism.

08.10.2025 <https://archive.ph/cNEsE>

CARPENTIER, NICO; DOUDAKI, VAIA, The Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy: A Tool for Democratic Renewal. Department of Communications Seminar, Universitas Islam Indonesia, Yogyakarta, Indonesia. July 24, 2025. <https://medemap.fsv.cuni.cz/wp->

[content/uploads/2025/08/communication-iii-ac-id-international-seminar-citizen-parliament-on-media-and-democracy-a-tool-for-democratic-renewal-.pdf](#)

CARPENTIER, NICO, DOUDAKI, VAIA, & HROCH, MILOS, (July 17, 2025). The PAR-fication of Citizen Parliaments: A Reconsideration of Participatory Intensities, IAMCR 2025, Singapore (13-17 July 2025).

ŠIMKOVÁ, KAROLÍNA, & WIMMER, JEFFREY, (July 14, 2025). The future was in the past: How Czech citizens perceive current struggles and threats to democracy and media, IAMCR 2025, Singapore (13-17 July 2025).

ŠIMKOVÁ, K., & WIMMER, J. (2025, July 6). Threats to the democratic role of media: The case of the Czech Republic. Ceecom 2025, Zadar, Croatia.

Roundtable. Media for Democracy: Roundtable on Strengthening Media and Democracy in Czech Society. *Média pro demokracii: Kulatý stůl o posilování médií a demokracie v české společnosti*. 05.06.2025

Roundtable. Democratic wellbeing: Democracy and media in Europe. 7th Weizenbaum Conference. 05.06.2025

CARPENTIER, NICO (2025) The democratic roles of European media: Threats and struggles, Media Studies and Perspectives 5 conference, Wrocław University, Wrocław, Poland (12-13 May 2025), invited keynote.

DOUDAKI, VAIA; CARPENTIER, NICO; FILIMONOV, KIRILL (2025) “Conditions of possibility for democratic media in Europe: A theoretically informed rereading of empirical literature”, DGPUK2025, Berlin, Germany (19-21 March 2025).

ŠIMKOVÁ, KAROLÍNA; WIMMER, JEFFREY (2025) “A horde of elephants in the room: Perceived threats to Czech media landscape”, ReMeD Conference, Prague, Czech Republic (10-11 February 2025).

DOUDAKI, VAIA; CARPENTIER, NICO (2025) “Conditions of possibility for democratic media in Europe”, ReMeD Conference, Prague, Czech Republic (10-11 February 2025).

CARPENTIER, NICO (2025) “Political struggles over media’s democratic roles: A discursive-material approach”, ReMeD Conference, Prague, Czech Republic (10-11 February 2025).

CARPENTIER, NICO (2024) “Democratic hybridities: A Model to Emphasize Struggles of Democracy and Media”, 7th Conference on Communication, Culture and Media Studies (CCCMS), Universitas Islam Indonesia, Yogyakarta, Indonesia (28 – 29 August 2024), invited keynote.

CARPENTIER, NICO (2024) “The Struggle over Participation: How to Rescue Participation from the Online Media Practices and Critiques”, Communication as Co-Creation IAMCR preconference, Western Sydney University, Sydney, Australia (27 June 2024), invited keynote.

CARPENTIER, NICO (2024) “The Contingency of Media’s Democratic Roles: A Discursive-Material Perspective”, ICA conference, Gold Coast, Australia (20-24 June 2024).

Presentations for the MeDeMAP Consortium

CARPENTIER, NICO. The Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy, Citizen parliaments – learnings for democratic innovation round table, Sixth MeDeMap consortium meeting, St. Pölten, Austria, 24-26 September 2025.

CARPENTIER, NICO (2024) “PARifying Citizen Parliaments –The Reconciliation of Two Participatory Models”, Mapping Media for Future Democracies – MeDeMap, Fourth Plenary Meeting, Jagiellonian University, Kraków, Poland (18 – 20 September 2024).

HROCH, MILOŠ (2024) “Czech Citizen Parliament Participant Recruitment Strategies”, Mapping Media for Future Democracies – MeDeMap, Fourth Plenary Meeting, Jagiellonian University, Kraków, Poland (18 – 20 September 2024).

CARPENTIER, NICO (2024) “Democratic Hybridities: A Model to Emphasize Struggles of Democracy and Media”, Mapping Media for Future Democracies – MeDeMap, Fourth Plenary Meeting, Jagiellonian University, Kraków, Poland (18 – 20 September 2024).

DOUDAKI, VAIA (2024) “Conditions of possibility for democratic media”, Mapping Media for Future Democracies – MeDeMap, Fourth Plenary Meeting, Jagiellonian University, Kraków, Poland (18 – 20 September 2024).

Film essay

AGON: a film essay (and artistic-academic project), originating from the MeDeMAP book “Democracy and Media in Europe”, reflecting on the political struggles that define democracy. <https://culcorc.fsv.cuni.cz/constructionsofdemocracy/>

Avant-premiere screening at the 6th MeDeMAP consortium meeting, Fachhochschule St. Pölten, St. Pölten, Austria (24 – 26 September 2025).

Première: AGON: Constructions of Democracy. Prague’s Ponrepo Kino, on 23 October 2025 at 13:00. Avant-première: screening at the 6th MeDeMAP consortium meeting, Fachhochschule St. Pölten, St. Pölten, Austria (24 – 26 September 2025).

MINANTO, A., CARPENTIER, N., & PURWANTO, J. S., (2025). AGON: Constructions of Democracy, Flow34, IAMCR 2025, Singapore (13-17 July 2025).

MINANTO, A., CARPENTIER, N. & PURWANTO, J. S. (2025). AGON: Construcciones de democracia/AGON: Constructions of Democracy, *Tecmerin. Revista de Ensayos Audiovisuales*, 16, 2025(2).

CU - Infographics:

Infographic 1: Czech Citizen Parliament Resolutions (EN)

Infographic 2: Czech Citizen Parliament Resolutions on Community Media (EN)

Infographic 3: Czech Citizen Parliament Resolutions on Media and Information Literacy (EN)

How Czech Citizens Reimagine the Role of the Media in Democratic Societies

A MeDeMAP Project

It takes a decade of citizen deliberation on public issues and generates actionable policy recommendations.

In parallel to part of the EU MeDeMAP Project:

- 28 citizens' assemblies from across the Czech Republic deliberated
- 4 meetings held in Prague, Brno, and Olomouc (March–July 2023)
- Participants to be key stakeholders: media, media law, journalism, education, and digital literacy
- Deliberative expert inputs and facilitated group discussions, concluded by voting resolutions
- 31 Resolutions addressing the media's role in strengthening Czech democracy, were developed
- Resolutions include a clear introduction, background, impact of the community media, and their conditions for journalists

6 KEY AREAS & 31 RESOLUTIONS

Strengthen Journalism

- Establish a legal framework for freelance journalists, regional & community media (RP-01)
- Establish a fund for independent regional media (RP-02)
- Support the use of advertising by local/regional government media to ensure independent local media (RP-03)
- Facilitate professional knowledge sharing in regional and community media (RP-04)

Ethics & Accountability

- Establish a code of ethics for journalists (RP-05)
- Establish a code of ethics for media owners (RP-06)
- Establish a code of ethics for media regulators (RP-07)
- Establish a code of ethics for media consumers (RP-08)

Local Journalism & Media Support

- Establish a legal framework for freelance journalists, regional & community media (RP-01)
- Establish a fund for independent regional media (RP-02)
- Support the use of advertising by local/regional government media to ensure independent local media (RP-03)
- Facilitate professional knowledge sharing in regional and community media (RP-04)

Funding Public Media & Regulating Market Media

Resolutions presented at Czech Senate on June 5, 2025. Outcomes will continue informing future policymaking and academic research in the Czech Republic, EU, and beyond.

Read the full Resolutions Report

Read more about the European Citizen MeDeMAP project

Partners: European Union, MEDEMAP

The Czech Citizen Parliament's Resolutions about Community Media

A MeDeMAP Project

What are Community Media?

Community media: an media owned and operated by citizens, voluntary, education, environment, and the local media. They are made to serve the community, not for profit, and are not subject to the same regulations as commercial media.

How did the Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy work?

28 Citizens' Assemblies from across the Czech Republic deliberated 4 meetings held in Prague, Brno, and Olomouc (March–July 2023)

Participants to be key stakeholders: media, media law, journalism, education, and digital literacy

Deliberative expert inputs and facilitated group discussions, concluded by voting resolutions

31 Resolutions addressing the media's role in strengthening Czech democracy, were developed

Resolutions include a clear introduction, background, impact of the community media, and their conditions for journalists

The Czech CP's five Resolutions on Community Media

- Make community media sustainable**
 - Provide subsidies for local, regional & community media (RP-01)
 - Create grant programmes to support media projects from regions, minority groups and people with insufficient representation in the media (RP-02)
 - Establish a legal framework for financing independent, regional & community media (RP-03)
 - Prevent the use of advertising by local/regional government media to protect independent local media (RP-04)
- Protect community media from political influence**
 - Facilitate professional knowledge sharing in regional and community media (RP-04)
- Build capacity in the community**
 - Facilitate professional knowledge sharing in regional and community media (RP-04)

Which examples already exist in the Czech Republic? Who can we learn from?

- Radio 8 (radio.cz)** – A public radio owned by citizens, operating since 2008. Open to all citizens and covering entire Czechia.
- Radio (radio.cz)** – A public radio established in 2002, providing news, rights and consulting advice to citizens across the Czech Republic.
- Radio Proxima (radio.proxima.cz)** – A 24/7, all-the-time community radio founded in 1995, focusing on local media and civil society in the Czech Republic.
- Radio Region (radio.region.cz)** – A 24/7, all-the-time community radio founded in 1999, focusing on local media and civil society in the Czech Republic.

Why do these resolutions matter?

The resolutions aim to ensure that community media are not subject to the same regulations as commercial media, and that they are able to provide a platform for citizens to voice their views on public issues.

Partners: European Union, MEDEMAP

The Czech Citizen Parliament's Resolutions about Media and Information Literacy

A MeDeMAP Project

What is Media and Information Literacy?

Media and information literacy is an umbrella term for skills, knowledge, attitudes and values that enable people to access, understand, evaluate, create and act on media and information in a responsible and ethical manner.

How did the Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy work?

28 Citizens' Assemblies from across the Czech Republic deliberated 4 meetings held in Prague, Brno, and Olomouc (March–July 2023)

Participants to be key stakeholders: media, media law, journalism, education, and digital literacy

Deliberative expert inputs and facilitated group discussions, concluded by voting resolutions

31 Resolutions addressing the media's role in strengthening Czech democracy, were developed

Resolutions include a clear introduction, background, impact of the community media, and their conditions for journalists

The Czech CP's Eight Resolutions for Media and Information Literacy

- Improve media education**
 - Create grant funds for media education and training (RP-05)
 - Strengthen media education and its evaluation in schools (RP-06)
 - Finance media to provide training for representatives of diverse social groups to become external media contributors (RP-07)
 - Create scholarship programmes for media students from minority groups (RP-08)
- Encourage learning by doing**
 - Establish a legal framework for financing independent, regional & community media (RP-03) and provide subsidies for local, regional & community media (RP-01)
 - Establish an open and definitive feedback forum on media content (RP-09)
- Create training and lifelong learning opportunities**
 - Establish a legal framework for financing independent, regional & community media (RP-03) and provide subsidies for local, regional & community media (RP-01)
 - Establish an open and definitive feedback forum on media content (RP-09)

Which examples already exist in the Czech Republic? Who can we learn from?

- JNS.CZ** – An educational program for people to build literacy skills, support development of media literacy, media critical thinking, media literacy, media literacy, media literacy, and active citizenship in the Czech Republic.
- Other Internet Centre (OtherInternetCentre.cz)** – A non-profit organization, led by CS and other NGOs, providing education, media literacy, and a platform for citizens to voice their views on public issues in the Czech Republic.
- Fakescap** – A non-profit organization, led by CS and other NGOs, providing education, media literacy, and a platform for citizens to voice their views on public issues in the Czech Republic.
- Beepool** – A non-profit organization, led by CS and other NGOs, providing education, media literacy, and a platform for citizens to voice their views on public issues in the Czech Republic.

Why do these resolutions matter?

The resolutions aim to ensure that media and information literacy is not subject to the same regulations as commercial media, and that it is able to provide a platform for citizens to voice their views on public issues.

Partners: European Union, MEDEMAP

MIC (Ireland) – Dissemination activities

For up-to-date information, see <https://www.mic.ul.ie/MeDeMap?index=4>

The Resolutions Report of the Irish Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy

https://issuu.com/micireland/docs/report_-_national_citizens_parliament_on_media_an?fr=sN2NjOTg0MzIzMjM

- **Academic publications and presentations**

Journal Article: McInerney, Jude, Rosemary Day and Kathy Cush “Irish Citizens’ Parliament maps out the future needs of the news media to support democracy” *In progress*

Journal Article: ‘Irish Audiences’ navigation of news platforms and their understanding of democracy’, Day, R and J McInerney in ESSACHES, in press (see Giulia Ferri, Elisabetta Risi and Andrea Miconi)

Journal article: Day, Rosemary and Jude McInerney, “The Challenges of bringing the news to the Irish public today” Submitted for peer review for *Volume 19, Issue 1 (37) / June 2026* of ESSACHESS – *Journal for Communication Studies*.

Book Chapter: ‘Challenges of bringing the news to the Irish Public’, McInerney and Day in book to be edited by Beata Klimkiewicz, Josef Seethaler and Jeffrey Wimmer (due February 10th 2026)

- **Papers and presentations**

Paper: McInerney, Jude, “Irish audiences’ understanding of the relationship between media and democracy” MeCCSA, Sandbox (Oct 2025)

Paper: McInerney and Day: Regulation and Accountability in a Hybrid Media System: ‘Irish Audiences’ Navigation of News Platforms’ (C U. Prague Feb 2025)

Paper: Day, R and J McInerney: The National Citizen’s Parliament of Ireland as an Intervention for Media and Democracy at Peripheries and Connections: Media, Communication, and Transformation IAMCR, UCG, (June, Galway 2026)

Presentation: Day, R: Countering Disinformation through Media Literacy Collaborations: From National Strategies to Local and Community Media, Media Literacy Ireland Conference (MIC 23 June 2025)

Presentation: Day, R: Media Research Forum of Ireland (MURFI), DCU, Dublin: ‘Citizens Parliament as a research tool’ (Dublin, Oct. 2025)

Paper: Day, R and J McInerney: Facilitating Public Engagement in mapping the Future Needs of the Media to support Democracy: The Irish National Citizens’ Parliament as example” at Beyond the Audience: Rethinking Participation and Power in the Age of Data Capitalism, IULM, Rome, Jan 15-16, 2026

Presentation: Cush, Day, McInerney: Irish National Citizens’ Parliament as research methodology. MIC, February 2026

- **Conferences**

Paper: McInerney, Jude, “Irish audiences’ navigation of a news platforms” at Regulation and Accountability in a Hybrid Media System Conference, CU, Prague, February 2025

Day, Rosemary, “The National Irish Citizens’ Parliament and Disinformation” at Countering disinformation through Media Literacy collaborations: From National Strategies to Local and Community Media Conference, MIC, June 2025

Day, Rosemary, “Facilitating public engagement in mapping the future needs of the media to support democracy: The Irish National Citizens’ Parliament as example”, at Beyond the Audience: Rethinking Participation and Power in the Age of Data Capitalism Conference, IULM, Rome, Jan 15-16, 2026

Day, Rosemary, “The National Citizens’ Parliament of Ireland as an intervention for Media and Democracy” at Peripheries and Connections: Media, Communication and Transformation Conference, IAMCR, UCG, June 2026

- **Presentations with Political Impact**

At level of local democracy:

Presentation by citizens to Limerick City and County Council, July 2025.

<https://www.mic.ul.ie/mic-insights/irish-national-citizens-parliament-present-at-the-july-meeting-of-limerick-city-and>

At level of national democracy:

Presentation by citizens to Joint Oireachtas Committee (Parliamentary Committee) on Arts, Media, Communications, Culture and Sport. 5.11.2025. <https://www.mic.ul.ie/mic-insights/medemap-november-update-on-citizens-parliament-ireland>

Briefing by Day, Rosemary at the inaugural national forum on disinformation and media literacy: <https://www.mic.ul.ie/news/2025/mic-hosts-inaugural-national-forum-on-disinformation-and-media-literacy>

At level of EU Parliament and Commission:

Presentation by citizens to MEPs and members of the EU Commission in Brussels, January 2026

NATIONAL CITIZENS' PARLIAMENT ON MEDIA AND DEMOCRACY, IRELAND

Mary Immaculate College,
Limerick

Image: King John's Castle, Limerick City, Ireland, Copr. IMCI

MEDEMAP

Funded by the EU through HORIZON, the National Citizens' Parliament of Ireland is part of the MeDeMap research project.

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the agency can be held responsible for them.

MI (Slovenia) – Dissemination activities

Dissemination activities	What?	Audience	Place & Time	Link
National Report CP Slovenia Media & Democracy with resolutions as PDF (EN)	The Slovenian Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy (EN)	National decision-makers and institutions, Media, Civil society, Citizens	Available to download online from repository and distributed via mailing lists and social media	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/ANG_zahtev_e-zbora_booklet-web.pdf
National Report CP Slovenia Media & Democracy with resolutions as PDF (SI)	The Slovenian Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy (SI)	National decision-makers and institutions, Media, Civil society, Citizens	Available to download online from repository and distributed via mailing lists and social media	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/zbor-obcanov_web.pdf
Public presentation of CP resolutions	Public presentation	National decision-makers and institutions	Ministry of Culture, Ljubljana; June 9th 2025	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/zahteve-zbora-obcank_ov-o-medijih-in-demokraciji/
Paper presentation: Slovenian Journalism – Between a Watchdog Role and a Watched Dog on a Roll	Conference	Academia	15th Central and Eastern European Communication Conference in Zadar; June 6th-7th 2025	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/en/journalism-audiences-and-platform-power-in-the-age-of-transformation/
Paper presentation: Community and Non-Profit Media in Slovenia: Persistent Marginalization in Media Policy and Landscape	Conference	Academia	Communication and Capital(ism) conference in Ljubljana; August 28th - 30th 2025	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/en/affect-and-capitalism/
Presentation of CP resolutions	Public broadcaster programme RTVsmo	General public	Public broadcaster; 1st Programme; July 5th 2025	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/zahteve-zbora-obcank_ov-o-medijih-in-demokraciji-v-oddaji-rtvsmo/

Presentation of MeDeMAP project findings (focus on CP resolutions)	Public presentation on journalism festival Naprej/Forward	Journalists and interested public	Maribor; November 14th 2025	https://www.mirovni-institut.si/en/uniform-media-diverse-publics-how-do-we-move-forward/
Presentation of MeDeMAP project findings (focus on CP resolutions)	N1 media outlet podcast	General public	Online; November 22th 2025	https://n1info.si/podkast/strast-do-odgovornosti/
Paper presentation: “Engaging Citizens in Shaping Media Futures: Democratic Participation in Slovenian Media Policy-Making” (Lori Šramel Čebular, Tjaša Turnšek, Brankica Petković)	Conference Beyond the Audience: Rethinking Participation and Power in the Age of Data Capitalism	Academia	IULM University, Rome, 15-16 January 2026	https://www.medemap.eu/?page_id=1577
Public presentation of the CP results	Public presentation	Stakeholders, journalists and general public	Ljubljana, end of February 2026	

THE CITIZENS’ PARLIAMENT DEMANDS ON MEDIA AND DEMOCRACY IN SLOVENIA

Appendix 3: Leaflets

Leaflet 1: Good practices of Media and Information Literacy in Austria, the Czech Republic, Ireland and Slovenia

Good Practices of Media and Information Literacy in Austria, the Czech Republic, Ireland and Slovenia
in line with the findings of the Citizens' Parliaments on Media and Democracy

Credit: Daniela Eckl

Media and information literacy is fundamental to pro-democratic media policy. This is evident from the resolutions adopted by the four Citizens' Parliaments on Media and Democracy, held in Austria, the Czech Republic, Ireland and Slovenia between March and May 2025.

Citizens' parliaments on Media and Democracy were organised as part of the project **Mapping Media for Future Democracies (MeDeMAP)**, involving partners from academia and civil society in ten EU countries. All teams examined the relationship between media and democracy and citizens' demand for more participation. The research project was coordinated by the Austrian Academy of Sciences (OeAW) and funded by the Horizon Europe programme.

Each of the Citizens' Parliaments on Media and Democracy comprised 20 citizens. These were organised by COMMIT (Austria), Charles University (Czech Republic), Mary Immaculate College (Ireland) and the Peace Institute (Slovenia). During four sessions dedicated to the topics of media and democracy, systems, representation, and participation, the citizens adopted resolutions in support of media policies that would strengthen democracy in their respective countries. Further details of the sessions can be found on the Citizens' Parliaments' blog <https://medemap.commit.at/medemap-blog/>

Media and Information Literacy is the ability to access, analyse, evaluate and create messages in a variety of contexts. It helps discern bias, recognize misinformation, resist hate speech, and actively engage in civic life, promoting informed decision-making in today's complex digital world (UNESCO).

Media literacy should not be limited to learning about tools and technologies, but should aim to equip people with the critical thinking skills required to exercise judgment, analyse complex realities and recognise the difference between opinion and fact. (EC 2023)

In line with the resolutions adopted by the Citizens' Parliaments on Media and Democracy, examples of good practice in media and information literacy are presented from **Austria, the Czech Republic, Ireland and Slovenia**.

Austria

Acknowledging the significance of information and media literacy in fostering civic engagement, the Austrian Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy adopted five resolutions aimed at promoting media literacy among all age groups.

WIENXTRA-Medienzentrum – media education and youth work

The Medienzentrum is part of Vienna's youth services and supports young people aged 10 to 22 in realising their own media projects. It offers workshops, advice, equipment rental, studios and editing rooms free of charge to young people and young professionals. The Medienzentrum also offers media education training for young people on a variety of topics.

Medienzentrum for youth workers

<https://wienextra.at/medienzentrum/>

<https://wienextra.at/jugendarbeit/informationen/themen-highlights/thema/medienbildung-und-digitale-jugendarbeit/>

COMMIT – Community Medien Institute

COMMIT connects community media with adult education. It offers a variety of formats for teaching critical media literacy to media professionals and adult education trainers. These range from short webinars to multi-day courses within the framework of political education.

COMMIT <https://www.commit.at>

COMMIT also provides learners with access to a wide range of freely available materials.

Media.Law.Ethics

<https://www.commit.at/materialien/handreichungen-und-schulungsunterlagen/medienrechtethik>

The Czech Republic

The Czech Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy adopted eight resolutions on media and information literacy. They call for a structured media literacy policy for all, as well as funding for organisations dedicated to media literacy. The Czech Republic is a member of the Central European Digital Media Observatory (CEDMO).

One World in Schools (JSNS) - Media Education in Primary Schools

One World in Schools (JSNS), a project by People in Need, focuses on media education in primary and secondary schools by offering comprehensive audiovisual lessons, teacher training, and interactive seminars. Over 4,000 schools utilize JSNS resources to boost media literacy and critical thinking about information quality, fake news, and social issues. The project organises "Media Literacy Weeks", which includes a day-long educational and networking event called the Media Education Fair.

JSNS - One World in Schools <https://www.jsns.cz/en/projects/media-education-in-primary-schools>

People in Need - Media Literacy Weeks <https://www.peopleinneed.net/jns-media-literacy-weeks-educational-events-discussions-with-journalists-and-materials-for-teachers-11431gp>

Safer Internet Centrum ČR - Internet safety and digital literacy

The Safer Internet Centrum ČR (SIC CZ) is dedicated to promoting internet safety and digital literacy across the country. The center operates through three pillars: prevention (educational programs for children, teachers, parents), helplines (24/7 crisis lines for those facing online risks), and a hotline for reporting illegal digital content. Operating as part of European networks (Insafe and INHOPE), SIC CZ partners with organizations like JSNS to deliver workshops and public awareness campaigns targeting online risks. It is an official partner of the European Commission for Safer Internet topics.

Safer Internet Center <https://www.bezpecnyinternet.cz/en/about-us/>

EU- Better Internet for Kids <https://better-internet-for-kids.europa.eu/en/sic/czech-republic>

Fakescape - Teaching media literacy through games

Developed by students from Masaryk University in 2018, Fakescape creates educational games designed to help participants recognize fake news and strengthen critical thinking. The games are tailored for primary and secondary school students, as well as adults. It aims to promote media literacy across different age and demographic groups in a playful, interactive way.

Fakescape <https://fakescape.cz/en/fakescape-en/>

Ireland

The Irish Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy has expressed concern that audiences may not be sufficiently protected or informed to engage fully in the country's democratic processes, or to make critical judgements. The members adopted several resolutions to promote media literacy for all, emphasising the importance of responsible digital citizenship.

Media Literacy Ireland

Media Literacy Ireland is an independent association committed to promoting media literacy across Ireland. It is funded by Ireland's media regulator, Coimisiún na Meán. The association has over 250 volunteer members, including representatives from NGOs, academia, and teachers.

Media Literacy Ireland provides individuals, teachers, youth workers and trainers with advice on how to counter disinformation and protect themselves and others. It aims to empower people to access and critically evaluate content and services across all platforms so they can participate effectively in the public sphere. The association runs courses and advertising campaigns on national and social media.

Media Literacy Ireland <https://www.medialiteracyireland.ie/>

The Media Literacy (MLI) Awards recognise efforts to empower citizens, particularly those within communities, to develop their media literacy skills. The awards are supported by Coimisiún na Meán.

<https://www.medialiteracyireland.ie/awards/>

Algowatch received the MLI award for the Best Media Literacy Initiative for Young People in 2025. This European project focuses on educating the general public about the challenges of algorithms and artificial intelligence in relation to information and digital citizenship.

<https://algowatch.eu/>

The Media Literacy Ireland Conference 2025 – Supporting communities, fostering citizenship, promoting democracy

The Media Literacy Ireland Conference, which took place in Dublin in November 2025, focused on 'Supporting Communities, Fostering Citizenship, Promoting Democracy'. The event provided an opportunity for networking and the exchange of ideas across the media literacy community. It also welcomed international speakers from Germany, Ukraine and Moldova. Over 90 people from various sectors across Ireland attended, including members of the Webwise youth panel who offered valuable insights into the views of young people.

<https://www.medialiteracyireland.ie/the-media-literacy-ireland-conference-2025/>

Slovenia

The Slovenian Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy has emphasised that media literacy should be strengthened at every stage of formal education, supported by teacher training and integrated across subjects, and complemented by tailored programmes for adults and other groups outside schools. It has also urged national and European authorities, as well as media outlets themselves, to foster media literacy and citizen empowerment to improve participation in democratic life.

Časoris - News for children and youth

Časoris is a non-profit online media outlet that produces news and explanatory journalism specifically for children and young people. The content is written in accessible language, contextualised for younger audiences and often accompanied by educational materials for use in schools. The outlet helps young readers to develop critical reading habits in a safe, age-appropriate media environment.

Časoris <https://casoris.si>

Državljan D – Media literacy workshops for youth

Državljan D implements workshops for young people that focus on critical media consumption, understanding power relations in digital platforms, and recognising misinformation, hate speech, and manipulation. The workshops combine practical examples from everyday media use with participatory discussion formats, encouraging youth to reflect on their own role as media users and potential content creators.

Državljan D <https://www.drzavljan.si>

AKOS (The Agency for Communication Networks and Services of the Republic of Slovenia) – Media and information literacy portal (MIPI)

Coordinated by the Agency for Communication Networks and Services of the Republic of Slovenia (AKOS), the Media and Information Literacy Portal (MIPI) serves as a central public resource for media literacy education. It brings together educational materials, research, tools and examples of good practice for educators, parents, journalists and the general public. The portal promotes cross-sector collaboration and guarantees the long-term availability of reliable, high-quality media literacy resources.

MIPI <https://www.mipi.si>

Funded by the European Union

Publishing Information:

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Edited by Laurence Monnot and Helmut Peissl (COMMIT) with partners contributions from Charles University (CZ), Mary Immaculate College (IE) and the Peace Institute (SLO).

Layout: Verena Hochleitner

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Leaflet 2: Good practices of community media and media participation in Austria, the Czech Republic, Ireland and Slovenia

Good practice of community media and media participation in Austria, the Czech Republic, Ireland and Slovenia in line with the findings of the Citizens' Parliaments on Media and Democracy

Credit: Petra Moser/FRO

Community media supporting citizens **participation in the media** are fundamental to a pro-democratic media policy. This is evident from the resolutions adopted by the four Citizens' Parliaments on Media and Democracy, held in Austria, the Czech Republic, Ireland and Slovenia between March and May 2025.

Citizens' parliaments on Media and Democracy were organised as part of the project **Mapping Media for Future Democracies (MeDeMAP)**, involving partners from academia and civil society in ten EU countries. All teams examined the relationship between media and democracy and citizens' demand for more participation. The research project was coordinated by the Austrian Academy of Sciences (OeAW) and funded by the Horizon Europe programme.

Each of the Citizens' Parliaments on Media and Democracy comprised 20 citizens. These were organised by COMMIT (Austria), Charles University (Czech Republic), Mary Immaculate College (Ireland) and the Peace Institute (Slovenia). During four sessions dedicated to the topics of media and democracy, systems, representation, and participation, the citizens adopted resolutions in support of media policies that would strengthen democracy in their respective countries. Further details of the sessions can be found on the Citizens' Parliaments' blog <https://medemap.commit.at/medemap-blog/>

Community media originate locally and use horizontal production structures, enabling people to create their own means of cultural expression, news, information and dialogue. They encourage debate within and outside of communities, promote democratic participation and contribute to a diverse media landscape. The Council of Europe recognises the value of community media as a source of local content, cultural and linguistic diversity, media pluralism, social inclusion and intercultural dialogue.

In line with the resolutions adopted by the Citizens' Parliaments on Media and Democracy, examples of good practice of community media supporting citizen participation in the media are presented from **Austria, the Czech Republic, Ireland and Slovenia**.

Austria

The Austrian Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy emphasised the importance of greater diversity within the media landscape. They also highlighted the need for increased public support for community media to encourage civic participation and strengthen democracy.

The **Association of Community Broadcasters in Austria** (Verband Freier Rundfunk Österreich) was founded in 1993 and brings together 14 non-commercial community radio stations and three community TV stations with up to 5000 active citizens involved. It runs an online platform where all involved citizens can upload their radio productions and make them available as podcasts for further distribution and exchange.

The association organises the annual School Radio Day. <https://www.freier-rundfunk.at/schulradiotage.html>

Thematic focus week with participation of all community broadcasters. <https://www.freier-rundfunk.at/themenschwerpunkte.html>

The "Land of Free Media" initiative: With its five independent, non-commercial radio stations and a community TV station, Upper Austria is the Austrian federal state with the greatest diversity of com-

community media. DORFTV, Radio FRO, Freies Radio Freistadt, Freies Radio Salzkammergut, Freies Radio B138, and FRI - Freies Radio Innviertel – have joined forces to form the “Land of Free Media” initiative. Together, they create media spaces for debates about politics and society, helping citizens to shape them. <https://landderfreienmedien.at>

The Czech Republic

The Czech Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy recognises the importance of community media and is calling for a media law that would grant official status and funding to media projects created by local or minority groups, including training initiatives. It also calls on the media to enable citizens to participate more in news creation.

Radio R

Radio R is a community radio station based at Masaryk University in Brno. Since its establishment in 2008, it has operated as a non-commercial, alternative and open platform, emphasising community building and creative expression. Radio R enables its members to create programmes covering diverse and minority topics, and offers students and volunteers without professional backgrounds hands-on experience in broadcasting.

Radio R <https://medzur.fss.muni.cz/studentska-media/radio-r>

Romea.cz

Romea.cz is a key community media outlet for the Roma community. Publishing news in both print and online formats, it reports on politics, culture, and human rights and highlights Roma perspectives, which are often absent from Czech mainstream media. Romea.cz also runs Roma TV and has a strong social media presence. Its mission is to combat racism, promote human rights and foster understanding between the Roma community and the majority population.

Romea.cz <https://romea.cz/en>

Ireland

The Irish Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy recommends that, in an era of globalisation, people should be able to inform themselves from a local source and recognises the role of community media. Resolutions adopted by citizens call for state support and collaboration between community media and other media organisations, particularly with regard to training.

CRAOL - The National Forum for Community Radio in Ireland

Since its foundation in 1995, CRAOL has served as a network, training facility and lobbying group for Irish community radio. Every week, 2,000 community radio volunteers broadcast to 170,000 people across Ireland through 21 fully licensed stations and almost 30 aspirant stations.

As a signatory to the AMARC Europe Charter, CRAOL's primary aim is to empower community broadcasters to deliver social benefits to their communities through active volunteering, shared resources, good governance, partnerships, and networking.

The community radio stations belonging to CRAOL are non-profit organisations, owned and managed by their communities. They promote inclusion, diversity, participation, and democracy.

CRAOL <https://craol.ie/>

Saturday Chronicles

Saturday Chronicles is a Community Radio show on Scariff Bay Community Radio based in Scariff, Co. Clare, promoting democracy and encouraging media literacy. It won the CRAOL Gold Medal in the Social Benefit and News category in 2025.

Scariff Bay Community Radio Podcasts SBCR

<https://scariffbayradiopodcasts.podbean.com/e/live-from-brussels%C2%A0-%C2%A0-interview-highlights-liam-hayes/>

Slovenia

Recognising the democratic importance of media participation, the Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy in Slovenia calls for citizens and civil society to be actively involved in agenda-setting, for a plurality of voices with legally guaranteed participation of women, minorities, and other underrepresented groups, and for the encouragement and support of grassroots and community media as platforms for democratic engagement, alongside education and policies that empower all citizens.

Oštro – Public editorial meetings

Oštro, a non-profit investigative media outlet, regularly organises public editorial meetings. Citizens are invited to participate in discussions about editorial priorities, story selection and journalistic dilemmas. These meetings increase transparency around the decision-making processes involved in journalism and introduce participants to the standards of investigative journalism, fact-checking and ethical responsibility. They also create meaningful opportunities for citizens to engage with journalism beyond passive consumption.

Oštro <https://www.ostro.si>

Radio Študent – Media production by marginalised groups

Radio Študent is a non-profit community radio station that gives citizens and marginalised and minority communities the opportunity to create and broadcast their own radio shows. The station provides access to media production tools and editorial support, as well as an established public platform. This enables groups that are often under-represented in mainstream media to express their perspectives, cultural identities, and political concerns and to participate in the public debate.

Radio Študent <https://radiostudent.si>

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